

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D1.5 Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM v1.0

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project
5G	5th Generation
AR	Augmented Reality
AWGN	Additive White Gaussian Noise
BLER	Block Error Rate
BS	Base Station
BW	BandWidth
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
CP	Control Plane or Cyclic Prefix
CQI	Channel Quality Indicator
CSI-RSRP	Channel State Information Reference Signal Received Power
CU	Central Unit
DC	Dual Connectivity
DL	Downlink
DU	Distributed Unit
E2E	End to End
eMBB	enhanced Mobile BroadBand
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
EU	European Union
FDD	Frequency Division Duplex
FRMCS	Future Railway Mobile Communication System
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
FWA	Fixed Wireless Access
GA	Grant Agreement
gNB	5G NodeB
GPS	Global Positioning System
IMT-2020	International Mobile Telecommunications-2020 (ITU standard for 5G)
IMT-Advanced	International Mobile Telecommunications-Advanced (ITU standard for 4G)
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
IoT	Internet of Things

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LOS	Line Of Sight
LTE	Long Term Evolution
MEC	Mobile Edge Computing
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MOS	Mean Opinion Score
MR-DC	Multi-Rat Dual Connectivity
MTBF	Mean Time Before Failures
NGC	Next Generation Core
NGMN	Next Generation Mobile Networks
NLOS	Non-Line of Sight
NR	New Radio
NSA	Non-StandAlone
PDCP	Packet Data Convergence Protocol
PDCCH	Physical Downlink Control Channel
PDSCH	Physical Downlink Shared Channel
PDV	Packet Delay Variation
PI	Performance Indicator
PUCCH	Physical Uplink Control Channel
PUSCH	Physical Uplink Shared Channel
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RRC	Radio Resource Control
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
RSRP	Reference Signal Received Power
RSRQ	Reference Signal Received Quality
RTT	Round Trip Time
SDU	Service Data Unit
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
SS-RSRP	Synchronization Signal - Reference Signal Received Power
SS-RSRQ	Secondary Synchronization Signal - Reference Signal Received Quality

SS-SINR	Synchronization Signal - Signal to Interference and Noise Ratio
SSB	Synchronization Signal Block
SUL	Supplementary Uplink
TCP	Transmission control protocol
TDD	Time Division Duplex
TTI	Transmission Time Interval
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UC	Use Case
UE	User Equipment
UL	Uplink
UP	User Plane
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
V2V	Vehicle to Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle to Everything
VRU	Vulnerable Road User

1 Executive Summary

The aim of this project is to conduct advanced field trials of most representative and innovative Connected and Automotive Mobility (CAM) applications, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G End to End (E2E) interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitized motorways, railways and shipways throughout Europe. The scope of the project spans the borders of 3 European Union (EU) member states (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions and their seamless functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor.

This deliverable will focus on defining the methodology for a comprehensive and robust test analysis of the 5G network features within a cross-border context that are essential for the CAM use cases developed in 5G-ROUTES. Working closely with the partners defining the scenarios to be validated in cross-border field trials, formats for a suite of test cases will be specified to measure the functionality and performance of the innovative solutions being put forward. These test artefacts will be captured based on the methodology developed that will enable them to integrate seamlessly with the development process. It is ensured that the CAM testing strategy examines the improvement over previous 4G capabilities.

The testing methodologies in the report builds on the expertise and results of other projects, such as 5G-TOURS, 5G-MOBIX, 5G-EVE, but also on Next Generation Mobile Networks (NGNM) Alliance Testing Methodology reports, Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) and International Telecommunication Union (ITU) documents. These methodologies cover testing of network Performance Indicators (PI) to ensure 5G network capabilities for all the test locations and use-cases in the scope of 5G-ROUTES. It starts from describing the network level PIs following with the methodologies for validating and testing. For this deliverable it was decided to go with the PIs and not to cluster them into a higher-level Key Performance Indicators (KPI) as it is not needed for network validation. However in the later stages of the project the KPIs can be selected if needed – those will be described then in D1.6.

This deliverable gives the overview of the PIs and their test methodologies at the current state of the project (end of month 16 of implementation). The final version of this report (deliverable D1.6, due in month 36) will be adjusted by the insights gathered from the first phase of the large-scale trials execution.

2 Introduction

The purpose of the deliverable is to define methodologies for the testing and validation of 5G features for the CAM trials of 5G-ROUTES project

2.1 Mapping 5G ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map 5G ROUTES's Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to 5G ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G ROUTES GA Component Title	5G ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
D1.5 Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM v1.0	Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM v1.0	Chapter 4	Chapter 4 describes the methodologies for validating 5G features
T1.3 Methodology for cross-border collaboration on CAM testing	<i>Task will focus on defining the methodology for a comprehensive and robust test analysis of the 5G features and the CAM use cases developed in 5G-ROUTES within a cross-border context</i>	Chapter 3 Chapter 4	<i>Chapter 3 describes the cross-border context Chapter 4 describes the test methodologies</i>
	<i>Task will specify formats for a suite of test cases to measure the functionality and performance of the innovative solutions being put forward</i>	Chapter (S4.2) 4	<i>Section 4.2 is specifying formats for the test cases</i>
	<i>Ensuring that the CAM testing strategy examines improvement over previous 4G capabilities</i>	S3.2.2	<i>In S3.2.2 the improvement over 4G will be examined</i>

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

2.2.1 Deliverable structure

The structure of the document is as follows:

Chapter 1 and 2 contain the general introduction of the deliverable and the 5G-ROUTES project.

Chapter 3 gives the overview of the general setup and requirements for testing and examines the cross-border focus and improvement over Long-Term Evolution (LTE).

Chapter 4. The main objective of this chapter is to describe the network level Performance Indicators (PI) and to describe the methodologies for testing and validating those PIs.

Chapter 5. Conclusions of the deliverable

2.2.2 Relation to other deliverables

The relations between this deliverable and others within the 5G-ROUTES project are illustrated on Figure 1.

Current deliverable describes how the use-cases could benefit from using 5G instead of 4G, describes the PIs for validating network features and how to measure them.

The requirements for KPIs (technical, business and service level) are described in the deliverable D1.9, the use cases and scenarios are defined in D1.1. The latest version of deliverable D1.3 describes the 5G network requirements, architecture and the deployment in the trial sites. The latest version of deliverable D1.7 defines the methodology and the toolset for both the technological performance and business validation of the use cases.

The output of D1.5 will be used to validate the 5G network before (and if needed also during) the use-case trials. The data from the measurements will be collected in the Tenant Web (D2.7).

Figure 1. Relation between deliverable D1.5 and other deliverables

2.3 Linkage to other project outputs

In this section the interdependencies with other project activities are specified. Namely, the deliverables from which this report utilized inputs and the deliverables to which this report provides its outputs.

Table 2. Linkage to other project outputs

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	Deliverable Chapter(s)	Contribution and Value of linkage
INPUTS from other deliverables utilised in this report		
D1.1 Use cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM	S3.1.2 S3.2.2	The input of radio access types per use-cases and indicative values of the performance of different commercial and experimental communication networks for real time services came from D1.1
D1.3 Report on 5G-ROUTES CAM deployment plan and longer-term deployment strategies	S3.1.1	The input to the deployment setup section came mainly from D1.3
D1.7 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results	Chapter 4	Synchronization between topics covered
D1.9 Use cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM	Chapter 4.1	Synchronization between network and service level KPIs
OUTPUTS from this report utilised by other deliverables		
D1.7 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results	Chapter 4	Synchronization between topics covered
D2.5 AI-based positioning enhancements v1.0	Chapter 2	Network performance measures defined in D1.5 are used to quantify positioning technology being used for the use-cases in 5G-ROUTES trials.
D3.1 Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM v1.0	Section 4.2 Section 3.1.4 Section 3.1.5	After network deployment it is important to go through the measurement processes described in D1.5 S4.2 for assessing the capabilities of the 5G network to deliver. The reporting plan and measuring tools used can be obtained from sections 3.1.4 and 3.1.5
D4.3 5G CAM field trials v1.0	Chapter 4	Before the field trials it is important to go through the network measuring results.
D4.6 Report on performance evaluation and lessons learned v1.0	Chapter 4	The final results from the network measurements should be gathered

3 General requirements and validation methodologies

In this chapter the general setup and requirements for the trials will be described including brief description of the trial sites and the deployment setup, traffic load, reporting, the measurement tools used and the network validation methodologies.

3.1 General setup and requirements

One of the main goals of the 5G-ROUTES project is to test pre-commercial CAM use-cases on end-to-end testbeds and to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications (REL 16 and 17) of CAM under realistic conditions, which can reflect near real-life network performance. To validate the network PIs in the best possible way and to keep the collected data comparable in different test locations, some general requirements should be listed.

3.1.1 Deployment setup

The use-cases and trials planned in WP1 will cover many different deployment scenarios - starting from lab trials, followed by localized trials at strategic cross-border locations (Valga/Valka twin-city, Tallinn & Gulf of Finland) and finally in larger-scale trials covering significant portions of transport routes along the selected corridor.

The scenarios include indoor hotspots (micro cells) on a ferry, macro cells for dense urban deployment and large macro cells with long range radios for covering the ferry path. These scenarios for providing enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) and Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communication (URLLC) services are based on NGMN and 3GPP [4][5] recommendations and are with following attributes:

Table 3. Indoor hotspot (Micro cell) deployment setup

Attributes	Expected Values
Carrier Frequency	3,5GHz Time Division Duplex (TDD)
System bandwidth	100 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	eMBB:30 kHz URLLC: 60 kHz
Cyclic Prefix (CP) length	2.3 μ s for eMBB, 1.2 μ s for URLLC
Transmission Time Interval (TTI)	eMBB: 0.5ms (14 symbols), URLLC: 0.125ms
Number of Layers	4
Base Station (BS) antenna elements	Up to 256 Tx and Rx antenna elements (minimum 64 is recommended, however 4 is commercially available)
User Equipment (UE) antenna elements	Up to 8 Tx and Rx antenna elements (minimum 4 is recommended and commercially available),
User location and speed	100% Indoor, 3km/h
Inter Site Distance	Up to 20m

Table 4. Macro cell deployment setup

Attributes	Expected Values
Carrier Frequency	3,5GHz TDD
Aggregated system bandwidth	100 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	eMBB:30 kHz, URLLC: 60 kHz
Cyclic Prefix (CP) length	2.3 μ s for eMBB, 1.2 μ s for URLLC
TTI	eMBB: 0.5ms (14 symbols), URLLC: 0.125ms
Number of Layers	4

BS antenna elements	Up to 256 Tx and Rx antenna elements (minimum 64 is recommended and commercially available)
UE antenna elements	Up to 8 Tx and Rx antenna elements (minimum 4 is recommended and commercially available)
User location and speed	100% outdoor (up to 120km/h)
Inter Site Distance	Up to 2000m

Table 5. Large Macro cell deployment setup

Attributes	Expected Values
Carrier Frequency	700MHz Frequency Division Duplex (FDD)
Aggregated system bandwidth	10 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	URLLC: 15 kHz
Cyclic Prefix (CP) length	1.2 μ s for URLLC
TTI	URLLC: 0.125ms
Number of Layers	4
BS antenna elements	Up to 8 Tx and Rx antenna elements
UE antenna elements	Up to 8 Tx and Rx antenna elements (minimum 4 is recommended and commercially available)
User location and speed	50% Indoor (3km/h) and 50% outdoor (30km/h)
Inter Site Distance	Long range antenna, distance up to 50km

The trials conducted in the 5G-ROUTES project will be based on the 5G Stand Alone (SA) architecture, which is defined both 3GPP REL16 and REL17 (if available) standards.

The classification of use-cases per radio service type described in D1.1 are in the Table 6.

Table 6. Radio access type per use-cases

ID	Title	Large macro	Macro	Micro
1.1	Dynamic vehicles platooning (V2V)		X	
1.2	Cooperative lane change		X	
1.3	See through view for safe automated overtake		X	
2.1	Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control		X	X
2.2	Traffic jam chauffeur		X	
3.1	Sensor info sharing		X	
3.2	Connected maintenance		X	
3.3	VRU collision avoidance		X	
4.1	360o immersive multi-user gaming on the go			X
4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go			X
5.1	Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross-border logistics	X	X	
5.2	5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight	X	X	X
5.3	FRMCS telemetry operation		X	X

3.1.2 Trial sites

In this section, trial sites, where the cross-border trials will take place, are briefly described. These trials are located in Valga-Valka, in Riga (Bikernieki racetrack) and on the bay between Tallinn and Helsinki. More detailed description about these sites, locations, the site selection and others are in the latest version of D1.3, D3.1 and in D3.5.

3.1.2.1 Riga Bikernieki Racing circuit

Before starting trials at Valga/Valka, the initial testing for some of the automotive use cases will need to be done in a highly controlled environment. Bikernieki racetrack in Riga will provide this option. A virtual cross border scenario is envisaged to be demonstrated with two 3,5GHz mobile sites – one site for LMT (Latvian) and the other for Telia (Estonian). The racetrack provides ample space to perform handovers between the “countries” and even perform high speed tests. Additionally, a temporary intersection can be built for use cases requiring its existence.

3.1.2.2 Road crossing between Estonia and Latvia (Valga/Valka)

The main area for trialing CAM use-cases is on the Estonian-Latvian border crossing in the twin city of Valga/Valka. Two junctions were selected - one on both sides of the border based on existing MNO, road, and city infrastructure. Even though it would be beneficial to merge the MNO infrastructure setup for both railway and CAM use cases from cost perspective, there was no rail and road border crossing available that could be covered with one-two base stations. The railway crossing is located at one edge of the city, the road border crossing on the other. Therefore, a limited cooperation between both uses cases located on the border between Latvia and Estonia was met. Nevertheless, initial estimate indicates that almost 5 km of rails/roads will be covered with 5G connectivity by two national operators.

3.1.2.3 Rail crossing between Estonia and Latvia (Valga/Valka)

The only border-crossing of trains between Estonia and Latvia is located in Valga/Valka. The trainline is ran by PV (Pasažieru Vilciens) and their trains make two trips in both directions between Riga and Valga.

There will be a 3,5GHz 5G base-station in both sides of the border (operated by LMT in Latvia and Telia in Estonia). The railway section, which crosses the Estonian-Latvian border, between the stations of Valga and Lugaži will be used.

3.1.2.4 Ferry between Tallinn and Helsinki

A mobile 5G base station will be installed on a ferry of Eckerö Line, M/S Finbo Cargo, which is operating on the line between Vuosaari port on the outskirts of Helsinki and the port of Muuga near Tallinn. M/S Finbo is mainly targeted towards freight transport, but can also carry up to 300 passengers. The vessel makes 2-3 daily trips between Helsinki and Tallinn in each direction.

The 5G network covering the ferry route will consist of 2 long range 700MHz 5G base stations – located in Muuga (Telia EE) and in Vuosaari (Telia FI). Also, there will be a 3,5GHz small cell base station on board of the ferry backhauled by a radio link and backed up with satellite service.

3.1.3 Traffic load

For usable and realistic results, it is important to generate a realistic traffic load in the field trial conditions. As the field test sites are somewhat remote then we cannot expect much of a commercial traffic on those sites. Therefore, generating artificial load is important. For this, several simultaneous connections with different UE-s can be used.

3.1.4 Reporting

The conducted field trial results will be analyzed and validated within the 5G-ROUTES consortium and made publicly available for following projects. In the 5G-ROUTES project we use the Tenant Web portal for displaying these results.

The quality of reporting is a vital step and must include enough details so adequate decisions could be based on these. The following aspects are recommended by NGMN in their framework definition [1], which could be used as a “template” for the case of 5G-ROUTES.

3.1.4.1 Trial setup information

Following deployment parameters need to be reported for each trial:

- Carrier frequency
- Operating bandwidth
- Duplex mode (e.g. FDD, TDD)
- Sub-carrier spacing
- Cyclic prefix
- TTI
- Number of sites and test UEs
- Type of environment (dense urban, urban, rural...)
- Site locations including coordinates and height information and a map with the site layout
- Test UEs location and height information
- BS and UE transmit power and antenna gain
- BS and UE antenna configuration (number of antennas, layout)
- BS and UE number of supported Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) layers
- Traffic type used for the trial.

3.1.4.2 Trial result information

The counters to be logged at the BS and UE sides are specified for each test case.

3.1.4.3 Trial result benchmarking

For having a meaningful baseline for benchmarking and to characterize the performance gain of NR to LTE it is important to define benchmarks to quantify the performance of 5G NR.

In 5G-ROUTES project we are using LTE Rel.15 as benchmark which helps quantifying the gains of NR as compared to LTE of the same release, but also to compare it to NR Rel.16 and Rel.17. There is also an option to have a middle step of using 5G NSA Rel.15 solution.

As 5G-ROUTES project is not focusing on LTE networks, we are not measuring any LTE network related details, but using the best practices available from consortium members Telia, LMT and Ericsson.

3.1.5 Measurement tools

As 5G is commercially available by the end of October 2021 in about 73 countries by more than 182 mobile operators (mainly Non-Stand Alone (NSA))[31], the availability and maturity of commercial devices has also evolved a lot. By the end of October 2021, 1115 5G devices have been announced, of which 600 are commercially available. 90.8% of the devices are supporting sub-6 GHz spectrum, however concrete bands and the combinations of the bands vary [3][31] hence the results of the measurement can vary. By the time of the measurements different UE-s must be tested – for that dedicated/ calibrated tools can be used.

There is also a possibility to use the calibrated Test and Measurement toolset for the testing, however given the normally higher capabilities of such devices, the results can be misleadingly good. A commercially available end

user device would give the generally available real-life experience. Despite of this drawback, a calibrated testing tool is used for some of the test-cases as the main measurement tool and for other test-cases as a reference tool.

In 5G-ROUTES project for network scanning and frequency testing Rohde & Schwarz TSME6 Drive Test Scanner and Rohde & Schwarz Freerider 4 Backpack will be used. These devices are ideal for tests on the road and while walking and to perform cellular network analysis in a very professional and advanced way.

Besides calibrated network scanners there will be used OnePlus 9 Pro mobile phones with QualiPoc software to get measurement data as realistic for the common user as possible.

3.1.5.1 UE pre-trial testing

A pre-trial calibration procedure should be established for all the UEs and BSs involved in the trail initiative.

Several types of tests should be included in the procedure:

- **Sensitivity tests:** these tests are aimed to identify the sensitivity of the device at different received power levels, including different types of interference. Starting from ideal no-noise conditions, including first Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) and scanning different Signal to Noise Ratio / Signal to Interference and Noise Ratio (SNR/SINR), then including adjacent channel interference and sweeping again different SNR/SINR. These tests require many iterations and sweeps, so a minimal number of PIs should be considered, such as throughput and latency.
- **Ideal baseline:** all the tests and PIs that will be evaluated in the field are tested in ideal conditions, with high SNR/SINR with no channel impairments, in order to have the maximum performance possible out of the device.
- **Realistic tests:** all the tests and PIs that will be evaluated in the field are tested with a set of pre-defined scenarios that represent realistic channel variations, including the behavior that the network would have with handovers. These tests will allow the understanding of how the PIs degrade in different complex and realistic scenarios.

In addition to the throughput testing, the tests should include the following:

- Basic Rx sensitivity on the channels and bandwidths required.
- Transmit power and power control.
- Modulation error and frequency accuracy up to high order QAM.
- Spectrum emissions and spurious domain.
- Basic protocols to allow cell selection, link establishment using 5G NR SA.

Upload and Download tests will be done using Iperf tool and using server closest to the UE.

3.2 5G Validation methodologies

In the 5G-ROUTES project the 5G network installed will be tested and validated that it suitable for the planned use-cases and that the Performance Indicators are on maximum level currently technologically available. The main benchmark for the PIs is described by ITU report M2410-0 [6] and shown on Table 7. However, it is understandable that all those conditions will not be met as we are in the beginning of the 5G technological evolution.

For validating the 5G network features the following methodology described in Figure 2 will be used:

Figure 2. 5G-ROUTES network validation

Network deployment plan is described in the latest version of D1.3 and the report on 5G infrastructure setup in D3.1. Test design phase is described with current document. Tests will be executed after network deployment, results will be analyzed and uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal. If the results are not satisfactory the network will be adjusted re-tested/analyzed.

3.2.1 Key Performance Indicators and Performance Indicators

Deliverable D1.1 describes the use cases and their requirements. Based on these requirements, the required performance with the PIs of the network is derived in D1.5. Those PIs will be measured for assessing the readiness of the 5G network for the use-cases. From those PIs the KPIs can be selected, if decided so in the next phases of the project. This will be described in D1.6

For the use-case specific indicators a methodology is worked out and the requirements given in D1.9 where several scenario dependant PIs are making a higher level composite KPI. Third type of performance indicators used in 5G-ROUTES project are the use-case specific Business KPIs, which are calculated from the input provided by the end-users during use-case trials. The selection of KPIs from PIs, if needed, is described in D7.3. The fragment of the performance measurement framework (fully defined in D7.3) is shown on Figure 3.

Figure 3. Fragment of the Performance Measurement Framework in 5G-ROUTES project from D7.3

3.2.2 Examining improvement over 4G

One of the main purposes of the 5G-ROUTES project is to validate the 5G networks and to show that it is much better suitable for CAM services than 4G. Although 4G, in its current state, is very mature and powerful there are hard requirements from CAM use-cases which need capabilities that a 4G network could not deliver. The most important of them all is latency.

On the Figure 4 is visualized the main differences between 4G and 5G.

Figure 4. Enhancement of key capabilities from IMT-Advanced (4G) to IMT-2020 (5G) [8]

It can be seen from the Figure 4 that the peak data rate of IMT-2020 for eMBB is expected to reach 10 Gbit/s. However, under certain conditions and scenarios IMT-2020 would support up to 20 Gbit/s peak data rate. IMT-2020 would support different user experienced data rates covering a variety of environments for eMBB. For wide area coverage cases, e.g. in urban and sub-urban areas, a user experienced data rate of 100 Mbit/s is expected to be enabled. In hotspot cases, the user experienced data rate is expected to reach higher values (1 Gbit/s indoor).

The spectrum efficiency is expected to be three times higher compared to IMT-Advanced for eMBB. The achievable increase in efficiency from IMT-Advanced will vary between scenarios and could be higher in some scenarios (for example five times subject to further research). IMT-2020 is expected to support 10 Mbit/s/m² area traffic capacity, for example in the hotspots.

The energy consumption for the radio access network of IMT-2020 should not be greater than IMT networks deployed today, while delivering the enhanced capabilities. The network energy efficiency should therefore be improved by a factor at least as great as the envisaged traffic capacity increase of IMT-2020 relative to IMT-Advanced for eMBB.

IMT-2020 would be able to provide up to 1 ms over-the-air latency, capable of supporting services with very low latency requirements. IMT-2020 is also expected to enable high mobility providing service with acceptable QoS when moving up to 500 km/h. This is envisioned in particular for high-speed trains.

Finally, IMT-2020 is expected to support a connection density of up to 10⁶ connections per km², for example in massive machine type communication scenarios.

Table 7 shows in more detail the differences of requirements for 4G vs 5G:

Table 7. Requirement evolution from LTE to NR

	LTE [7]	5G requirements ITU [6] and 3GPP [32]

Peak data rate	Downlink (DL): 1Gbps	DL: 20 Gbps Uplink (UL): 10 Gbps
User experienced data rate	DL: 10Mbps	DL: 100Mbps UL: 50Mbps
UP latency	10ms	eMBB: 4ms URLLC: 1ms
CP latency	100ms	20ms
Connection density	100 000 devices per km ²	1 000 000 devices per km ²
Reliability	1-10 ⁻²	1-10 ⁻⁵
Mobility	350km/h	500km/h
Positioning accuracy	N/A	Horizontal positioning error <= 50m for 80% of UEs Vertical positioning error <5 m for 80% of UEs
Mobility interruption time	27.5-60ms	0ms

Table 8, worked out in deliverable D1.1 S2.4, gives the indicative values of the performance of different commercial networks known today and the planned performance of the VTT test facility. In 5G-ROUTES project for the 5G network validation the aim is to get as close to ITU requirements for 5G (Table 7) as possible, however the exact success criteria is given under every network PI separately in chapter 4.

Table 8. Typical network performance [D1.1]

Category	Type	Commercial				VTT test facility
		4G	5G	GEO Satellite	LEO satellite (1)	
Network	Service area	country	country	continent	continent	VTT site
	Coverage	99%	99% (*)	99%	99%	100%
	Cross border	yes	yes	yes	yes	no
	Number of subscribers	>1e6	>1e6	>1e5	>1e5	10
	Simultaneous end users per cell	10 (*)	50 (**)	> 1000	> 1000	5
	Availability	99%	99%	99%	99%	N/A
Delay and jitter	Radio processing and propagation delay	40 ms	40 ms	300 ms	50 ms	40 ms
	Network delay	15 ms (*)	< 5 ms (**)	50 ms	< 5 ms (**)	5 ms
	Network jitter (internet)	30 ms (*)	< 5 ms (**)	30 ms	< 5 ms (**)	< 5 ms
Latency	Mobile to Fix latency	85 ms (*)	50 ms (**)	380 ms	60 ms	50 ms
	Mobile to Mobile latency	80 ms (*)	40 ms (**)	700 ms	100 ms	80 ms
Cross Border impact	Service continuity	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	N/A
	Roaming duration	> 1 mn	0.5- 1s (*)	0 s (**)	0 s (**)	N/A (***)
Throughput	Downlink (average per user)	10-20 Mbps	50-100 Mbps	2 Mbps (*)	4 Mbps (*)	20 Mbps
	Uplink (average per user)	2.5 Mbps	25 Mbps	250 Kbps (*)	500 Kbps (*)	10 Mbps
	(1) typical for mega constellation					

3.2.3 Cross-border focus

All the trials in 5G-ROUTES project have a high cross-border focus. Handover time is the main network PI that needs to be tested. This PI is an important metric which will also affect other PIs and therefore will be a vital component for the following use-cases:

- UC 1.1 Dynamic vehicle platooning
- UC 1.2 Cooperative lane change
- UC 1.3 See though view
- UC 2.1 Real-time traffic/ RT collision control
- UC 2.2 Traffic jam chauffeur
- UC 3.1 Sensor info sharing
- UC 3.3 VRU collision avoidance
- UC 4.1 360-degree multi gaming on the go
- UC 4.2 3D RT virtual collaboration on the go
- UC 5.2 Proactive and multimodal management of passengers and freight
- UC 5.3 Continuous railway infrastructure monitoring with optical sensors

It is also important to test how accurately the positioning works while handover is in progress and afterwards in roaming.

Handover from one network to another may also affect the data throughput, mobility, jitter and the overall QoE.

4 Trial measurements

This section will give an overview of the test methodologies used in this work. The chapter starts with defining the metrics needed for validating 5G network features. Later, the methodologies for comprehensive testing of those PIs will be given.

4.1 Network level Performance Indicators relevant for the trials

In the current document we focus on the 5G network level PIs to validate the network features and confirm that the network is able to provide the service needed for the use-cases to be tested and demoed. The use-case specific KPIs relevant to the 5G-ROUTES use-case scenarios are identified in the deliverable D1.9.

The sources of the PI definitions come from NGMN 5G Trial and Testing Initiative Pre-Commercial Network Trials Framework Definition [2], ITU-R M.2410-0 [6], 5G PPP Phase II KPI definitions [10], other 5G-PPP projects [11-14] and 3GPP documents [15].

The PIs defined in these documents are used to provide a performance evaluation of 5G systems and should be tested on both 3GPP REL-16 and REL-17. However, it currently seems REL-17 will not be available and implemented by the network device vendors in a time we could test its features in the scope of the 5G-ROUTES project [28].

In many cases, there are several methodologies given for testing a PI to make sure that all the different situations and trial sites would be covered.

Network level PIs are the requirements for 5G network to ensure the high-level communication between the road users and infrastructure in 5G-ROUTES project use-cases. Such PIs include data rate, mobility/ handover time, latency, jitter, connection density, reliability, positioning accuracy, coverage and availability.

The network level PIs (as in proposal) are displayed in Table 9:

Table 9. Network level PIs

Use Case Category	ID	Title	Network PIs							
			Data rate (Mbps)	Mobility (km/h)	E2E latency (ms)	Jitter (ms)	Density (vehicles /Km2)	Reliability (%)	Positioning accuracy (m)	Tho (ms)
1 - Automated Cooperative Driving	1.1	Dynamic vehicles platooning	N/A	<200	5	<0.5	>2 000	>99.99	<1	<10
	1.2	Cooperative lane change	N/A	<200	5	<0.5	>2 000	>99.99	<1	<10
	1.3	See through view for safe automated overtake	>50	<200	5	<0.5	>2 000	>99.99	<1	<10
2 -Awareness Driving	2.1	Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control	N/A	<150	<20	<0.5	>10 000	>99.99	<1	<10
	2.2	Traffic jam chauffeur	N/A	<150	<100	<0.5	>10 000	>99.99	<1	<10
3 -Sensing Driving	3.1	Sensor info sharing	N/A	<150	<10	<0.5	>2 000	>99.99	<0.5	<10
	3.2	Connected maintenance	<100	<250	<1 000	<0.5	>10 000	>99.99	N/A	<10
	3.3	VRU collision avoidance	N/A	<100	<20	<0.5	>2 000	>99.99	<0.5	<10
4 - Uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go	4.1	360o immersive multi-user gaming on the go	>100	<300	<10	<1	>10 000	>99	N/A	<10
	4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go	<200	<300	<20	<1	>10 000	>99	N/A	<10
5 - Multimodal services	5.1	Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross-border logistics	<250	Not Critical	Not Critical	Not Critical	<10^6	>99.9	<1	<10
	5.2	5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight	<250	<150	<20	<1	>10 000	>99.99	<1	<10
	5.3	FRMCS telemetry operation	<300	<100	<20	<1	-	>99.99	-	<10

Next, a more detailed information about each network level PI will be given.

4.1.1 Data rate

Data rate is the number of bits transmitted through the system per unit of time. There are several data rate KPIs related to the performance of 5G systems. In the 5G-ROUTES project the user experienced data rate and peak data throughput will be addressed. The definitions are based on ITU-R requirements for IMT-2020 [6].

In 5G network, compared to previous generations, main enhancement of data rate comes from higher spectral efficiency, utilizing a better MIMO scheme and increased bandwidth from new spectrum assets.

4.1.1.1 Peak data rate

Peak data rate is the maximum DL/UL data throughput achievable for a single user located at the best location within a cell.

Peak data rate is defined for a single mobile station. In a single band, it is related to the peak spectral efficiency in that band. Let W denote the channel bandwidth and SE_p denote the peak spectral efficiency in that band. Then the user peak data rate R_p is given by:

$$R_p = W \times SE_p$$

Peak spectral efficiency and available bandwidth may have different values in different frequency ranges. In case bandwidth is aggregated across multiple bands, the peak data rate will be summed over the bands. Therefore, if bandwidth is aggregated across Q bands, then the total peak data rate is

$$R = \sum_{i=1}^Q W_i \times SE_{p_i}$$

where W_i and SE_{p_i} ($i = 1, \dots, Q$) are the component bandwidths and spectral efficiencies respectively.

This requirement is defined for the purpose of evaluation in the eMBB usage scenario.

From the ITU requirement report [6], we find the minimum requirements for peak data rate as follows:

- Downlink peak data rate is 20 Gbit/s.
- Uplink peak data rate is 10 Gbit/s.

Those numbers could only be achieved by using much larger bandwidth of spectrum which is available in the 26GHz frequency band. Also, a massive MIMO solution would have to be used for which today there are no available end user devices.

For 5G-ROUTES use-cases 100MHz of 3.5GHz TDD spectrum, with 4 MIMO layers will be used. This provides us the theoretical peak maximums of up to 1,5Gbps for DL and 200Mbps for UL. We are using also 2*10MHz of 700MHz FDD spectrum in 5G-ROUTES. However, as we are not planning to test any eMBB use-cases there, the peak data rate is not relevant. Despite of that for information purposes we can mention that the DL peak data rate could be close to 170Mbps.

Much larger peak rates could be achieved by using frequency aggregation. In the 5G-ROUTES project we do not have LTE (or other bands) available for testing so carrier aggregation will not be used.

In this project, peak data rate is not as important PI as user experienced data rate, however it gives us a good starting point when evaluating the overall user experience.

4.1.1.2 User Experienced data rate

User experienced data rate is the 5% point of the cumulative distribution function of the user throughput. User throughput (during active time) is defined as the number of correctly received bits, i.e. the number of bits contained in the service data units delivered to Layer 3, over a certain period of time.

In case of one frequency band and one layer of transmission reception points (TRxP), the user experienced data rate could be derived from the 5th percentile user spectral efficiency through equation (3). Let W denote the channel bandwidth and SE_{user} denote the 5th percentile user spectral efficiency. Then the user experienced data rate, R_{user} is given by:

$$R_{user} = W \times SE_{user} \quad (3)$$

In case bandwidth is aggregated across multiple bands (one or more TRxP layers), the user experienced data rate will be summed over the bands.

This requirement is defined for the purpose of evaluation in the related eMBB test environment.

From the ITU requirement [6] report we find the target values for the user experienced data rate in the Dense Urban – eMBB test environment:

- Downlink user experienced data rate is 100 Mbit/s.
- Uplink user experienced data rate is 50 Mbit/s.

In 5G-ROUTES project user experienced data throughput is most relevant for the use-cases displayed in Table 10.

Table 10. eMBB use-cases and experienced data rate requirements

Use case	Required data rate DL/UL (Mbps)
UC 1.3 See through view	50/50
UC 4.1 360-degree multi gaming on the go	100/10
UC 4.2 3D RT virtual collaboration on the go	200/20

4.1.2 Mobility

Mobility is the maximum mobile terminal movement speed at which a defined QoE can be achieved (in km/h).

The following classes of mobility are defined:

- Stationary: 0 km/h
- Pedestrian: 0 km/h to 10 km/h
- Vehicular: 10 km/h to 120 km/h
- High-speed vehicular: 120 km/h to 500 km/h.

In the 5G-ROUTES project we are not looking into high-speed vehicular class, because the speed limits in Estonia and Latvia are up to 120km/h. Table 11 defines the mobility classes that shall be supported in the respective test environments.

Table 11. Mobility classes

	Test environments		
	Indoor Hotspot	Dense Urban	Rural
Mobility classes supported	Stationary, Pedestrian	Stationary, Pedestrian, Vehicular (up to 30 km/h)	Pedestrian, Vehicular

Mobility is an important characteristic for most of the use-cases tested in the 5G-ROUTES project.

4.1.2.1 Handover time

Handover time is the brief interruption time in which a mobile terminal cannot transmit or receive data when a mobile terminal is moving from a source cell to a target cell (as seen on Figure 5).

Figure 5. Handover of a mobile terminal from a source cell to a target cell [16]

In a 4G LTE deployment, the mobility interruption time is typically around 30 – 60 milliseconds [16] depending on handover scenario and effective radio conditions. However, to ensure the performance of emerging 5G wireless use cases, one of the big challenges for the 3GPP community has been to shorten this time to as close to zero milliseconds as is technically possible.

In today's 5G networks, such a short mobility interruption time is possible in a few scenarios, for example when the mobile terminal moves from one beam to another within the same cell.

The solution which is standardized as part of 3GPP Release 16 will bring shorter interruption times to more handover scenarios and deployments.

In the section 4.2.2.2 we describe testing methodologies for several different cases of handover like Intra-gNB, Inter-gNB, Intra-DU, Intra-CU etc. The most important scenario for cross-border focus is Inter Operator handover, where the mobile terminal is moving from an MNO from one country to an MNO in another country.

4.1.3 Latency

Latency is a very important parameter for enabling 5G use cases, particularly the URLLC use case for latency-critical applications in CAM. This section aims at demonstrating that pre-commercial 5G solutions (infrastructure, transport and devices) are meeting the expected latency performances through most significant testing configuration cases. Both control plane and user plane latencies are considered.

4.1.3.1 User plane latency

User plane latency is the contribution of the radio network to the time from when the source sends a packet until the destination receives it (in ms). It is defined as the one-way time it takes to successfully deliver an application layer packet/message from the radio protocol layer 2/3 SDU ingress point to the radio protocol layer 2/3 SDU egress point of the radio interface in either uplink or downlink in the network for a given service in unloaded conditions, assuming the mobile station is in the active state [6].

This requirement is defined for the purpose of evaluation in the eMBB and URLLC usage scenarios.

The minimum requirements for user plane latency are:

- 4 ms for eMBB
- 1 ms for URLLC

assuming unloaded conditions (i.e. a single user) for small IP packets (e.g. 0-byte payload + IP header), for both downlink and uplink. These can be, however, hard to be reached with current state of NR evolution and for 5G-ROUTES user plane latency <10ms would be satisfactory.

When considering latency requirements, the following important metrics are considered:

- E2E Latency between UE and Application Server: Measures the duration between the transmission of a small data packet from the application layer at the source node and the successful reception at the application layer at the destination node plus the equivalent time needed to carry the response back.
- Core Latency: The round-trip time between 5G NodeB (gNB) and the Application Server.

User plane latency between UE and Evolved Packet Core (EPC) or Next Generation Core network (NGC):

- measures the time it takes to transfer a small data packet from user terminal to the Layer 2 / Layer 3 interface of the 5G system destination node, plus the equivalent time needed to carry the response back;
- is seen as optional and could be considered for URLLC use case, for avoiding negative impact of delays outside the 5G system.

For URLLC, the target for user plane latency should be 0.5ms for UL, and 0.5ms for DL. Furthermore, if possible, the latency should also be low enough to support the use of the next generation access technologies as a wireless transport technology that can be used within the next generation access architecture. For eMBB, the target for user plane latency should be 4ms for UL, and 4ms for DL [20].

4.1.3.2 Control plane latency

Control plane latency refers to the transition time from a most “battery efficient” state (e.g. Idle state) to the start of continuous data transfer (e.g. Active state).

This requirement is defined for the purpose of evaluation in the eMBB and URLLC usage scenarios.

From 3GPP specification for Radio Resource Control (RRC) protocol [18], the RRC states related to the measurement of control plane latency can be described with the following diagram as shown on Figure 6:

Figure 6. NR UE RRC state and state transition [18]

The minimum requirement for control plane latency is 20ms, however lower latency, e.g. 10ms, could be acquired.

4.1.3.3 End-to-End latency

E2E latency is affected by the time needed for processing video, audio or sensor data on the UE side, by air interface transmission latency, core network processing latency and transport network transmission latency.

A sample of E2E latency could be seen on the Figure 7.

Figure 7. E2E latency sample [19]

E2E latency T_L is the time which includes the following components: processing time on the transmitter/receiver devices T_{proc} , over-the-air transmission delay in one-way T_{trans} , and the network processing time $T_{netproc}$ (i.e. the

BS and control server). Taking 1ms E2E latency T_L for instance, the distribution of the latency over various components can be as follows: 300µs for T_{proc} , 200µs for T_{trans} in both sides, and 500µs for $T_{netproc}$.

$$T_L = T_{proc} + 2T_{trans} + T_{netproc}$$

The processing latency, including the processing in the device T_{proc} and the processing in the network $T_{netproc}$, includes time for receiving data symbols, acquiring channel information, extracting control (scheduling) information, decoding data packet, and checking the existence of error [19].

As E2E latency is not a network level PI, the measurement of it is not covered in this document but in D1.9.

4.1.4 Jitter

Originally, jitter refers to the deviation of true periodicity of a signal. In networking it pertains to the variance in packet delay at the receiving side of a communication link. It quantifies the fluctuation in delay as packets are being transferred across a network. This effect can be experienced as a disruption in the normal sequence of sending data packets, which eventually may reflect even to network congestion and packet loss. A network with constant delay has no packet jitter. Packet jitter is expressed as an average of the deviation from the network mean delay and is an important QoS factor in assessment of network performance. Jitter can degrade the user experience and the QoS and therefore it is a major metric that should be evaluated and taken into consideration [21][22].

Jitter typically consists of various jitter components that are caused by different jitter sources as seen on Figure 8.

Figure 8. Jitter decomposition tree [9]

For the analysis of jitter, it is important to understand these sources and the contributions to the total jitter. For an analytical approach, a jitter model is frequently used, which splits jitter into the two major categories of random and deterministic jitter.

The jitter of the different components has different causes. Knowing what jitter component is influencing your system can help you identify what phenomenon causes the jitter.

Deterministic jitter

Deterministic jitter, also called systematic jitter, is further broken down into periodic jitter and data-dependent jitter. Deterministic jitter is bounded and specified as peak-to-peak value.

Periodic jitter

Periodic jitter is caused by a periodic disturbance. Though this signal is not necessarily sinusoidal, it is frequently also named sinusoidal jitter. The amplitude of the periodic signal bounds the jitter. A strong local RF oscillator, a switch-mode power supply, undesired crosstalk or an unstable, oscillating PLL cause period jitter due to an unintentional coupling into the signal.

Data-Dependent jitter

Inter-symbol interference causes data-dependent jitter. When ISI is present, the signal is disturbed with an attenuated, time-shifted copy of itself or spectral parts of itself.

Random jitter

Random jitter is unbounded and commonly specified by the standard deviation σ . Due to its irregular nature, random jitter is uncorrelated to any other signal and unpredictable in timing behavior. Contributions to the random jitter are thermal noise, shot noise, $1/f$ noise and other physical effects.

For 5G-ROUTES project we assess jitter in more general terms as a Packet Delay Variation (PDV).

4.1.5 Connection density

Up to several hundred thousand simultaneous active connections per square kilometer shall be supported for massive sensor deployments. Here, active means the devices are exchanging data with the network. Note this PI assumes a single operator in the considered area [1].

From the latest Ericsson mobility report (June 2021 edition) we can see that there are currently already more than 8 billion mobile devices around the world and it will reach to 8.8 billion in 5 years. Over that period, 5G subscription uptake is expected to be significantly faster than that of 4G (LTE). By the end of 2026 it is forecasted 3.5 billion 5G subscriptions globally accounting for around 40 percent of all mobile subscriptions at that time. 91 percent of the subscriptions in 2026 are projected to be mobile broadband. Fixed wireless access (FWA) connections are forecast to grow more than threefold and reach over 180 million by the end of 2026. The number of IoT connections will grow from 12.6 billion today to 26.4 billion on 2026 [26]. These figures confirm that massive connection density is one of the main KPIs that 5G should fulfill and depending on the use case needs, lighter or more challenging requirements should be guaranteed. In the context of the project, the estimated values have been provided for the use-cases in the following Table 12.

Table 12. Use-case requirements for connection density

Use case	Density requirement (devices/km ²)
UC 1.1 Dynamic vehicle platooning	>2 000
UC 1.2 Cooperative lane change	>2 000
UC 1.3 See through view	>2 000
UC 2.1 Real-time traffic/ RT collision control	>10 000
UC 2.2 Traffic jam chauffeur	>10 000
UC 3.1 Sensor info sharing	>2 000
UC 3.2 Connected maintenance	>10 000
UC 3.3 VRU collision avoidance	>2 000
UC 4.1 360-degree multi gaming on the go	>10 000

UC 4.2 3D RT virtual collaboration on the go	>10 000
UC 5.1 Goods tracking visibility in X-border logistics	<1 000 000
UC 5.2 Proactive and multimodal management of passengers and freight	>10 000
UC 5.3 Continuous railway infrastructure monitoring with optical sensors	N/A

The commonly agreed unit for measuring this metric is (users/devices per km²). For evaluating connection density different methodologies can be used.

The ITU-R M.2410 and M.2412 describe the methodology for evaluating density using system level simulation. This methodology is also used for 5G-ROUTES project and described more thoroughly in section 4.2.5.

In other projects connection density has also been evaluated via the number of users in RRC connected mode during each granularity period [33]. In 5G-EVE project the number of connected devices is taken from the NG-RAN node – 5G-ROUTES project will also use the information from network node as a comparison.

4.1.6 Reliability

Reliability is one of the main characterizing features of 5G where 5G NR is expected to add much improved performance in terms of reliability as compared to LTE. In 5G there are several methods introduced for rising reliability like the flexible frame structure, with various options for sub-carrier spacing, modulation and coding; the hybrid automatic repeat request, reference signals to improve synchronization, network slicing and highly available network topologies [34].

Reliability can be evaluated by the success probability of transmitting X bytes within a certain delay, which is the time it takes to deliver a small data packet from the radio protocol layer 2/3 SDU ingress point to the radio protocol layer 2/3 SDU egress point of the radio interface, at a certain channel quality (e.g., coverage-edge) [20].

A general URLLC reliability requirement for one transmission of a packet is $1-10^{-5}$ for 32 bytes with a user plane latency of 1ms.

For eV2X, reliability requirement for transmitting a packet of size 300 bytes is $1-10^{-5}$ with a user plane latency of 3-10 msec.

4.1.7 Positioning accuracy

Positioning accuracy is the difference between the position measured with a UE using 5G network for acquiring location and the actual horizontal position of a UE.

In 3GPP REL-16 (3GPP TR 38.855) [32] the defined positioning requirements for the regulatory use-cases are following:

- Horizontal positioning error ≤ 50 m for 80% of UEs
- Vertical positioning error < 5 m for 80% of UEs
- End to end latency and TTFF < 30 seconds

And for the commercial use-cases:

- Horizontal positioning error < 3m for 80% of UEs in indoor deployment scenarios
- Vertical positioning error < 3m for 80% of UEs in indoor deployment scenarios
- Horizontal positioning error < 10m for 80% of UEs in outdoor deployments scenarios
- Vertical positioning error < 3m for 80% of UEs in outdoor deployment scenarios
- End to end latency < 1s

In 3GPP REL-17 the requirements will be even more enhanced:

- Horizontal positioning error <0.3m (absolute, indoor/outdoor)
- Vertical positioning error <2m (absolute, indoor/outdoor)
- Positioning service latency <10ms

4.1.8 Coverage

In telecommunications, coverage area is the geographic area where the base station and the user device can communicate. [2] Coverage depends on several factors, such as the environment (mountains, etc.), weather, buildings, technology, radio frequency and sensitivity and transmit efficiency of the base station and the end user device. Coverage measurements usually comprises of two aspects:

- The availability. Signal strength above a defined minimum threshold, of those downlink signal components (e.g. broadcast channels, synchronization signals or reference symbols) in a geographical area, which are required to allow the end user device to synchronize with the base station and to obtain basic network information.
- The achieved service quality. Minimum data rate in case of mobile data services or a minimum speech quality in case of voice services, in a geographical area, which is required or defined.

The second aspect requires a communication link established between the base station and the end user device. Also, an interface into the end user device and base station, which enables the extraction of either measured or achieved parameters like signal strength or data rate. Additionally, the first aspect can be measured using passive measurement devices, so-called network scanners, that do not require an active communication link between the network scanner and the base station. Scanners provide reference data for the measurements performed by the end user device.

As an example, the SS-SINR measurement done in the end user device is a crucial measurement, since it will be the basis for Channel Quality Indicator (CQI) reporting to the network and eventually determines the achievable throughput in case of a data service.

Likewise, Synchronization Signal - Reference Signal Received Power (SS-RSRP) and Secondary Synchronization Signal - Reference Signal Received Quality (SS-RSRQ) are important measurements based on known reference symbols, which are performed in the end user device and reported to the network. Scanner equipment provides the same measurements based on known signals like broadcast channel, synchronization signals and reference symbols without affecting network operation. Although optional, it is highly recommended during trials and initial network installation phase to use scanner measurements in addition to end user device measurements/data.

Scanner data will serve as an independent source of measurement results since end user devices may be in prototype or pre-commercial stage. Furthermore, scanner generally provides better sensitivity and results that are more accurate.

There are several main objectives to be satisfied by coverage test cases:

- Coverage gap analysis between 4G and 5G. Depending on the 5G frequency bands and the legacy 4G frequency bands, there may exist a coverage gap even under the same propagation environment. It is important to understand this gap in diversified scenarios such as Urban Macro, Dense Urban, Urban roads, Rural, etc.
- Beamforming capability. Beamforming will be enabled in 5G BS with the help of active antenna systems, and both the data and the control signals will be pre-coded to boost signal quality. The beamforming benefits should be measured at cell edge.
DL Data/control channel coverage difference. The physical signals on the data channel will have different beamforming gain to that of the control channel. It is essential to identify the mismatch of coverage range between data and control channels, to ensure correct decoding at the UE. There are different DL control channel boosting schemes to help the situation. For example, dynamic beamforming or repeated transmission using a wide beam.
- UL coverage enhancement at UE. In addition to the power control mechanism, UE can have multiple antennas, and thus transmit diversity capability to aid UL coverage performance, e.g., UE Tx power is 23dBm without Tx diversity, or 26dBm with Tx diversity. There is also a discussion on shared/supplementary UL feature in 3GPP, where LTE frequencies will be used for NR UL data and/or control and NR frequencies still for DL. Since during the trials, the UL and DL are inseparable, better UL coverage will lead to better DL performance.
- UL coverage enhancement using Supplementary Uplink (SUL). 3GPP has proposed the SUL deployment option to solve the UL coverage problem (at 3.5GHz or nearby frequency bands), where the UL and DL are decoupled and UL can use lower frequency band than the DL (e.g. sub-1GHz or 1.8GHz) to enhance coverage. SUL will make the system design of 5G more complicated, i.e. the base station and the user terminal needs to handle multi-frequency operation, albeit this is in SA scenario.

It is also worth noting that inter-cell interference is known as the bottleneck of coverage performance in TDD networks. In the trials, the level of interference is controlled by the neighboring cells' traffic load on the UL and/or the DL. Both on data and/or control channels, otherwise it will be difficult to accurately quantify the interference imposed on the cell-under-test.

4.1.9 Availability

Network availability is the amount of uptime in a network system over a specific time interval [24]. Uptime refers to the amount of time a network is fully operational. Network availability is measured as a percentage and is monitored to ensure the service being provided is consistently kept running for end-users.

Network availability is typically recorded by real-time performance monitoring tools in a proactive manner. This allows networking professionals to catch pauses in availability as they happen. Additionally, most networks also provide users with reactive availability tools that allow them to submit a support ticket when the network becomes unavailable.

The uptime and availability of a network are important KPIs for network service providers to measure. Maintaining a certain level of network availability can help organizations with disaster planning, recognizing when issues arise and providing users with a standard quality of service.

Network availability is measured as the percentage of time a system stays fully operational over a period of time, usually over a year. Service providers will typically include a specified level of network availability in a Service Level Agreement (SLA).

$$\text{Availability} = \frac{\text{Uptime}}{\text{Total time (Uptime+Downtime)}}$$

The formula for availability is equivalent to the uptime divided by the total time, where the total time is uptime plus downtime. Measured downtime includes all times where the network system is down, such as for maintenance, unplanned failures or for the time it takes for a system to recover.

100% availability is considered to be when a network system is fully operational and available for its entire runtime. Typically, high availability will strive from around 99-99.999% (or the five 9's).

Network availability vs. reliability

Network reliability is similar to availability but instead of measuring the amount of uptime in a system, reliability is the measured likelihood of a failure occurring in a system. Reliability will track how long a network's infrastructure is functional without interruption. Network reliability is also measured in percentages, where a fully reliable system has 100% availability. Reliability can be calculated through either dividing the total time in service by the number of failures (known as Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF)) or by dividing the number of failures by total time in service (known as failure rate).

4.2 Test methodologies

When the previous section focused mainly on defining the 5G network level PIs, then the aim of this section is to describe all the different test methodologies for validating 5G features in 5G-ROUTES project. The main purpose is to have a described toolset to be used for testing in different locations and at the same time keeping the results comparable.

4.2.1 Data rate

The data rate section describes the test specifications for measuring peak data throughput and user experienced data throughput.

In 5G-ROUTES project eMBB use-cases are all verified in 3,5GHz network scenario thus eliminating the need of doing the data rate tests in 700MHz or other radio bands.

Data rate tests for URLLC and mMTC are voluntary.

4.2.1.1 Peak data rate

4.2.1.1.1 Test setup

Maximum achievable DL/UL data rate should be measured in the field environment. There should be only one UE in the cell under test, positioned in the ideal radio conditions. No other UEs should be placed in the surrounding cells. The test can be conducted in indoor or outdoor deployment scenario. Peak rate test should be executed in stationary scenario.

High-level test set-up is shown on Figure 9.

Figure 9. High level peak data rate test setup [2]

4.2.1.1.2 Test configuration

For the 5G peak data rate tests there are two use-cases: eMBB service and URLLC service. The configuration options for these are following:

- Conf. 1 (eMBB service):
 - Frequency band: 3,5GHz

- Sub-carrier spacing: 30 kHz
- Cyclic Prefix (CP) length: 2.3μs
- TTI: 500μs (14 symbols at 30kHz)
- Deployment options: Urban Macro
- System BW: 100 MHz for eMBB
- DL peak rate test: if dynamic UL/DL switching is not supported, minimum UL configuration
- UL peak rate test: if dynamic UL/DL switching is not supported, minimum DL configuration
- Conf. 2 (URLLC service):
 - Frequency band: 3,5GHz
 - Sub-carrier spacing: 60(30) kHz
 - CP length: 1.2μs
 - TTI: 125μs
 - System BW: 100 MHz
 - DL peak rate test: if dynamic UL/DL switching is not supported, minimum UL configuration
 - UL peak rate test: if dynamic UL/DL switching is not supported, minimum DL configuration

4.2.1.1.3 Test procedure

The following procedure for measuring peak UL/DL data throughput should be used:

1. Coverage of the test area defined as Received SS-RSRP > -60 dBm and SS-SINR > 22dB as measured with measurement tool.
2. Identify a location(s) where combination of highest MIMO rank, modulation and coding rate can be attained with stability.
3. Ensure that there are no UEs connected in any of the surrounding cells.
4. Connect 1 UE to the sector and ensure there is only this UE connected to the sector.
5. Measure L1 and PDCP layer throughput:
 - a. If dynamic UL/DL ratio is not supported, reconfigure the system for minimum UL DL/UL ratio
 - b. Download to the UE using UDP or TCP (using iperf) for DL peak test
 - c. Measure PDCP layer throughput (PDCP throughput is payload bits divided by the aggregated time) and L1 throughput using measurement tool; session duration should be at least 2 minutes; max./min./avg. value should be reported
 - d. Upload to the test server using UDP or TCP (using iperf) for UL peak test
 - e. Measure PDCP layer throughput (PDCP throughput is payload bits divided by the aggregated time) and L1 throughput using measurement tool; session duration should be at least 2 minutes; max./min./avg. value should be reported.

4.2.1.1.4 Success criteria

On wide range coverage eMBB use case with 100MHz of BW in 3,5GHz spectrum with 4x4 MIMO DL and 2x2 MIMO UL the 5G should deliver by the standard up to 1.5Gbps DL peak rate and 200Mbps UL peak rate with DDDSU slot configuration. However, for 5G-ROUTES use-cases up to 500Mbps DL and 100Mbps UL will be enough.

4.2.1.1.5 Logging

The following metrics should be logged on the UE side:

- DL throughput (PDCP, L1 and application layer)
- UL throughput (PDCP and L1)
- SS-RSRP

- SS-RSRQ
- SS-SINR
- DL BLER
- MIMO mode and rank

4.2.1.2 User experienced data rate

4.2.1.2.1 Test setup

There should be one UE under test. Static locations and/or drive route should be identified to cover the whole range of SINR. The drive route should cover different environments such as open areas, close to reflecting buildings, Line of Sight (LOS) and Non-Line of Sight (NLOS). The route should also consider different relevant inter-cell relations depending on used beam management features, such as direction in extension of neighbor cell BS to UE direction. There should be multiple static UEs (minimum 10) in all cells (evenly distributed in the cell/coverage area). Several loading load scenarios should be considered: no load, full load.

4.2.1.2.2 Test configuration

For the 5G user experienced data throughput tests there are two use-cases: eMBB service and URLLC service. The configuration options for these are following:

- Conf. 1 (eMBB service):
 - Frequency Band: 3,5GHz
 - Sub-carrier spacing: 30 kHz
 - CP length: 2.3 μ s
 - TTI: 500 μ s (14 symbols at 30kHz)
 - Deployment options: Urban Macro
 - System BW: 100 MHz for eMBB
 - DL peak rate test: if dynamic UL/DL switching is not supported, minimum UL configuration
 - UL peak rate test: if dynamic UL/DL switching is not supported, minimum DL configuration
- Conf. 2 (URLLC service):
 - Frequency Band: 3,5GHz
 - Sub-carrier spacing: 60(30) kHz
 - CP length: 1.2 μ s
 - TTI: 125 μ s
 - System BW: 100 MHz
 - DL peak rate test: if dynamic UL/DL switching is not supported, minimum UL configuration
 - UL peak rate test: if dynamic UL/DL switching is not supported, minimum DL configuration

4.2.1.2.3 Test procedure

The following procedure for measuring user experienced data throughput should be used:

1. Select cells pointing to the trial area and providing continuous coverage
2. Select drive route and/or static locations to cover the whole range of SS-SINR:
 - a. Cell edge should represent interference limited positions with SS-SINR < 0dB
 - b. Average conditions should be represented by SS-SINR (5dB to 10dB).
 - c. Good conditions should be represented by SS-SINR (15dB to 20dB)
 - d. Excellent conditions should be represented by SS-SINR > 22dB
3. Load surrounding cells by deploying the loading UEs or by activating load feature
4. Connect UE to the cell and perform download/upload to/from the UE using UDP or TCP (using iperf).

5. Measure PDCP layer throughput (PDCP throughput is payload bits divided by the aggregated time) and L1 throughput using measurement tool; session duration should be at least 2 minutes; max./min./avg. value should be reported.

4.2.1.2.4 Success criteria

The drive test results could be presented as a curve of throughput versus SS-SINR. The bandwidth and the UL/DL ratio for TDD need to be reported along with the results. Calculate the average data rate for each static measurement points.

eMBB use case; 3.5GHz, 100 MHz BW; indoor/ outdoor environment

- NGMN: 5G should provide 10x improvement on average and peak rates per user (eMBB use case).
 - Assuming practical LTE Rel'12 systems, 2.6 bits/s/Hz (Cat. 11/12) average DL spectral efficiency is assumed, 5G should deliver 260 Mbps average data rate.
 - Assuming practical LTE Rel'12 systems, 2.0 bits/s/Hz (Cat. 11/12) average UL spectral efficiency is defined, 5G should deliver 200 Mbps average data rate.
- ITU-R: The minimum requirements for average spectral efficiency for various test environments are:
 - 7.8 bits/s/Hz DL average spectral efficiency is assumed, 5G should deliver 780 Mbps average data rate.
 - 5.4 bits/s/Hz UL average spectral efficiency is assumed, 5G should deliver 540 Mbps average data rate.

4.2.1.2.5 Logging

The following metrics should be logged on the UE side:

- DL throughput (PDCP and L1)
- UL throughput (PDCP and L1)
- SS-RSRP
- SS-RSRQ
- SS-SINR
- DL BLER
- MIMO mode and rank

4.2.2 Mobility

This section focuses on intra-cell mobility and inter-cell mobility (handover) scenarios. Currently, it is probable that we could not test voice-call services in 5G with the next 3GPP releases 16 and 17, thus only packet switched data scenarios are considered with Standalone (SA) configuration.

On the field test trials there is no possibility to test high speed vehicular mobility (120 km/h to 500 km/h) due to speed limits in Estonia and Latvia.

4.2.2.1 Intra cell mobility

This section considers testing the intra-cell mobility for different UE speeds and angles. In addition, performance, throughput, packet loss in different mobility scenarios and for different services should be verified. We give different testing scenarios for maximum angle mobility and maximum doppler mobility.

4.2.2.1.1 Maximum angle mobility

Intra-cell mobility with different angles to transmission point is considered in this section. This section covers mobility without RRC, so some aspects of beam tracking are also included.

4.2.2.1.1.1 Test setup

Deployment Scenario: Rural, urban may also be possible for low speeds. One 5G NR cell is needed. Test cell covers angle of 120 degrees. There should be more than one UE in order to track beam accurately.

4.2.2.1.1.2 Test configuration

Drive test route is described on the Figure 10:

Figure 10. Drive test route for maximum angle mobility

For testing 3 different scenarios could be considered:

1. Test on 15km/h
2. Test on 60km/h
3. Test on 90km/h

4.2.2.1.1.3 Test procedure

1. 5G NR Base Station (and for NSA Multi-Rat Dual Connectivity (MR-DC) case LTE base station) is/are powered on and configured with related parameters
2. All the UE's are under 5G NR cell coverage.
3. UE's are powered on and complete initialization process.
4. UE's are successfully attached to the 5G network and are able to upload/download data.
5. All UE's start uploading/downloading data (e.g. from a file transfer protocol (FTP) server)
6. UE's should start movement from Measurement Point (MP) 0 and arrive at MP 4 on the route over the curve with an angle of 120 degrees as in Figure 10. Speed of the car should stay the same during the test.
7. Continuously monitor DL/UL throughput, latency, packet loss and signal strength of beam.
8. The scenario shall be repeated with different speeds of car as described in previous section

4.2.2.1.1.4 Success criteria

- PS service shall continue without interruption.
- DL/UL throughput, user plane latency and packet loss should be observed between MP0 to MP4.
- Beam signal strength variations should also be tracked based on Beam ID
- SS-RSRP/SS-RSRQ/SS-SINR variations should be observed.
- User plane latency variations should be recorded. For eMBB service, user plane latency should be less than 4ms and for URLLC user plane latency should be less than 1ms.

From the NGMN 5G whitepaper [1] 50 Mbps DL and 25 Mbps UL throughput is expected on minimum for mobile car.

4.2.2.1.2 *Maximum doppler mobility*

Intra-Cell Mobility during movement to and from a transmission point (Doppler Effect) is considered in this section.

4.2.2.1.2.1 *Test setup*

Deployment Scenario: Rural, urban

One 5G NR cell is needed.

One UE is enough to observe Doppler Effect.

4.2.2.1.2.2 *Test configuration*

Drive test route should be similar to the Figure 11:

Figure 11. Drive test route for maximum doppler mobility

4.2.2.1.2.3 *Test procedure*

1. 5G NR Base Station (and for NSA MR-DC case LTE base station) is/are powered on and configured with related parameters
2. The UE is under 5G NR Cell coverage.
3. UE is powered on and has completed initialization process.
4. UE is successfully attached to the 5G network and is able to upload/download data.
5. The UE starts uploading/downloading data.
6. UE should start movement from MP0 to MP1 with certain speed. Speed of the car should stay the same during the test.
7. Continuously monitor DL/UL throughput, latency, packet loss and SS-RSRP/SS-RSRQ/SS-SINR.
8. UE should start movement from MP1 to MP0 with same speed. Speed of the car should stay the same during the test.
9. Continuously monitor DL/UL throughput, latency, packet loss and SS-RSRP/SS-RSRQ/SS-SINR.
10. The scenario shall be repeated with different speeds of the car (15km/h, 60km/h, 90km/h).

4.2.2.1.2.4 *Success criteria*

- PS service shall continue without interruption.
- Better DL/UL throughputs should be observed at lower speeds.
- Packet loss should be lower at low speeds.
- SS-RSRP/SS-RSRQ/SS-SINR variations should be observed.

- User plane latency variations should be recorded and for eMBB service, user plane latency should be less than 10ms and for URLLC user plane latency should be less than 1ms.

From NGMN 5G whitepaper [1], 50 Mbps DL and 25 Mbps UL throughput is expected on minimum for mobile car.

4.2.2.2 Handover time

This section focuses on testing the SA handover from 5G NR cell to another 5G NR cell.

4.2.2.2.1 Test setup

Deployment scenario: rural, urban, dense urban. Number of 5G NR cells should be at least two in order to trigger Handover during the drive test. It is better to setup a cluster with more 5G NR cells.

The following metrics should be focused on during the test.

- Handover interruption time which is defined in the NGMN 5G Whitepaper as a time during which the user is not able to receive any user plane data, including inter-system authentication time, should be evaluated in different scenarios and configurations.
- DL and UL throughput variations and minimum DL/UL Throughput should be measured and verified during the handover
- Packet-loss rate due to the handover procedure at different OSI layers should be measured during the trial.

4.2.2.2.2 Test configuration

The tests should be performed for all the scenarios mentioned in the Table 13.

Table 13. Handover trial configuration

Speed range	0-15km/h	15-60km/h	60-90km/h
TCP	Config 1	Config 3	Config 5
UDP	Config 2	Config 4	Config 6

5G NR can be either a collapsed gNB (without Central Unit – Distributed Unit (CU-DU) split) or with CU-DU Split.

In 5G-ROUTES project we focus only on intra-band handover (Cell 1 and Cell 2 are in same band). The following cases should be performed:

- Scenario 1. Intra-gNB handover (without CU-DU split) within 5G NR.
 - Cell 1 and Cell 2 are in same gNB (Figure 12:- Scenario 1 and 2 for intra/inter-gNB handovers).
- Scenario 2. Inter-gNB handover (without CU-DU split) within 5G NR
 - Cell 1 and Cell 2 are in different gNB (Figure 12:- Scenario 1 and 2 for intra/inter-gNB handovers).

Figure 12. Scenarios for intra/inter-gNB handovers

- Scenario 3. Intra-DU handover within 5G NR
 - Cell 1 and Cell 2 are in same DU (Figure 13:- Scenario 3, 4 and 5 for handovers in CU-DU function split case).
- Scenario 4. Intra-CU inter-DU handover within 5G NR
 - Cell 1 and Cell 2 are under same CU but different DU (Figure 13:- Scenario 3, 4 and 5 for handovers in CU-DU function split case).
- Scenario 5. Inter-CU handover within 5G NR
 - Cell 1 and Cell 2 are in different CU (Figure 13:- Scenario 3, 4 and 5 for handovers in CU-DU function split case).

Figure 13. Scenarios 3,4 and 5 for handovers in CU-DU function split case

- Scenario 6 Inter-Operator handover
 - Cell 1 and Cell 2 are in different network as seen in the Figure 14 (operator A and operator B). This is the most important characteristics to measure the cross-border impact to the CAM use-cases.

Figure 14. Scenarios 6 Inter-Operator handover

4.2.2.2.3 Test procedure

1. 5G NR Base Stations are powered on and configured with handover related parameters (neighboring cells, thresholds etc.)
2. All the UEs are under Cell1 coverage.
3. UE's are powered on and have completed the initialization process.
4. UE's are successfully attached to the 5G network and are able to upload/download data.
5. All UE's start uploading/downloading data (e.g. from an FTP server)
6. For all scenarios above (scenario 1 to 6), UE should move from Cell 1 to Cell 2 with velocities 15km/h, 60km/h and 90km/h.
7. The handover procedure should be successfully performed for all UE's.

4.2.2.2.4 Success criteria and logging

Minimum 20 valid samples are required for result evaluation. The following metrics should be logged:

- DL and UL Throughput: DL/UL Throughput variations and Minimum DL/UL throughputs during handover at different speeds should be continuously monitored. From NGMN 5G whitepaper, 50 Mbps DL and 25 Mbps UL throughput is expected on minimum for a mobile car.
- Packet loss: It is necessary to report precisely in which layer the packet loss is measured in the trial:
 - At network layer (layer 3 in OSI model) - IP Packet Loss Rate (IP PLR)
 - At transport layer (layer 4 in OSI model) - TCP PLR or UDP PLR (equal to IP PLR)
 - At application layer (layer 5 in OSI model) - Block Error Rate (BLER) to evaluate the information loss
- Interruption time: User plane handover interruption time should be close to 0ms as in the 3GPP NGA requirements document [4]. This requirement is for handovers happening between gNB-s that belong to one MNO network. However, for Inter-Operator handover the requirement is looser.

4.2.3 Latency

In the following subsections the test setup with success criteria for UP latency and CP latency are being addressed.

4.2.3.1 User plane latency

4.2.3.1.1 Test setup

With the very small latency target by 5G, the transmission delay on the transport segment between the RAN and the core and finally the application server becomes more important. 1ms delay in the fiber corresponds to 200

km transmission. Consequently, the type of network architecture and the location of this application server are fundamental in the test setup definition.

This is the reason why two scenarios are defined for both eMBB and URLLC:

- A first scenario with typical deployment of centralized core network and the server more than 200 km away from the end user.
- A second scenario with the core network user plane gateway and the server very close to the RAN. It is the case of data steering to a local data network, such as the site of an enterprise. It can also be the Multiaccess Edge Computing (MEC) concept (local break-out to the application server).

4.2.3.1.2 Test configuration

For the 5G user plane latency tests there are two use-cases: eMBB service and URLLC service. The configuration options for these are following:

- Conf. 1 (eMBB service):
 - Sub-carrier spacing: 30 kHz for <6GHz deployment
 - CP length: 2.3us
 - TTI: 500us (14 symbols at 30kHz)
 - Deployment options: Urban Macro (< 6GHz)
 - System BW: no specific constraint but bandwidth value needs to be reported
 - Duplex mode: FDD mode, or TDD mode with DDDSU DL/UL ratio
- Conf. 2 (URLLC service):
 - Sub-carrier spacing: 60(30) kHz for <6GHz deployment
 - CP length: 1.2us
 - TTI: 125us
 - System BW: no specific constraint but bandwidth value needs to be reported
 - Number of layers: 1
 - Duplex mode: FDD mode, or TDD mode with DDDSU DL/UL ratio

4.2.3.1.3 Test procedure

1. Select sector pointing into the trial area.
2. Select a location in that cell (good, average and cell conditions) based on the cell grid:
 - Good conditions should be represented by $-90 \text{ dBm} < \text{SS-RSRP}$
 - Average conditions should be represented by $-100 \text{ dBm} < \text{SS-RSRP} < -90 \text{ dBm}$;
 - Cell edge conditions should be represented by $\text{SS-RSRP} < -100 \text{ dBm}$
3. Start traces on protocol analyzer
4. Measurement performed for both unloaded and loaded scenario. 70% network resource usage in all cells is recommended for the "Loaded scenario". This may be achieved using dummy traffic generator.
5. Perform multiple (1500) DL/UL standard size (32) pings over the UE under test to a local test server, and record Max, Min and Average ping times.
6. Derive the RAN Latencies on 5 (chosen around the average End to End Latency) of these 100 measurements:
 - With the protocol analyzer, capture the traffic over NG interface (in gNB) with high accuracy time stamping (decode the ping request/response from UE/PDN gateway over the appropriate GTP-U tunnel). This shall allow characterizing the round-trip time between gNB and the Application Server, defined here as core Latency. We consider that the Application Server is located closely to the EPC/NGC node.

- Calculate the DL/UL RAN Latency as the subtraction of the two previous values: RAN Latency = End to End Latency - Core Latency.

4.2.3.1.4 Success criteria

The 5G system should be able to provide 10ms E2E latency in general and 1ms E2E latency for the use cases which require extremely low latency. Note these latency targets assume the application layer processing time is negligible to the delay introduced by transport and switching.

The given objectives are referring to Round Trip Times (RTT) and are set for both RAN and End to End Latencies

For eMBB use case:

- RAN Latency ≤ 8 ms
- E2E Latency with 200 km distance between NR node and EPC/NGC + Application server $\leq 10-15$ ms

For URLLC use case:

- RAN Latency ≤ 1 ms
- E2E Latency within Local Data Network ≤ 2 ms
- E2E Latency with Operator network ≤ 3 ms

4.2.3.1.5 Logging

On the UE side, the following metrics should be available for performance assessment:

- SS-RSRP (Reference Signal Received Power)
- SS-RSRQ (Reference Signal Received Quality)
- User Plane Latency (when possible)
- E2E (End to End) Latency
- Ping Success Rate
- Packet Loss Rate

On the gNB side, the following metrics should be available for performance assessment:

- Latency from gNB to EPC/NGC

For logging latency results and success rate template as in Table 14 could be used.

Table 14. User plane latency test results logging

RF condition	Ran latency [ms]		EPC latency [ms]		E2E latency [ms]		EPC ping success rate (%)	EPC packet loss rate (%)	E2E ping success rate (%)	E2E packet loss rate (%)
	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX				
Good										
Average										
Cell edge										

4.2.3.2 Control plane latency

These tests are intended to validate different mobility state transitions (control plane) and their transitions times. More specifically, the tests aim to:

- Quantify “Idle to Connected”/ “Connected to Idle”, and “Inactive to Connected”/ “Connected to Inactive” state transition times.
- Verify the associated process for each type of state transition

4.2.3.2.1 Test setup

A basic configuration will be defined in order to facilitate implementation of tests and comparison of results.

A standalone architecture will be considered.

Number of users:

- Latency testing with a single user is the priority.
- (optional) A scenario with 10 users located under the same cell on average

Latency testing should be performed at several locations across the considered cell for ensuring different radio conditions.

Measurements should be performed in a loaded scenario. 70% network resource usage in all cells is recommended for the “Loaded scenario”. This could be achieved using dummy traffic generator.

For the NR RRC Inactive to NR RRC Connected transition time measurement in SA configuration, two cases shall be considered:

- UE triggered transition from NR RRC_INACTIVE to NR RRC_CONNECTED
- Network triggered transition from NR RRC_INACTIVE to NR RRC_CONNECTED

4.2.3.2.2 Test procedure

NR RRC Idle to NR RRC Connected latency in SA configuration

1. In the serving cell, start UE trace and UE power cycle.
2. 5G Core Network initiates UE Context Release Command messages, and then UE transmits Idle state.
3. Ping a server on the 5G Core Network to trigger a service request from UE.
4. Stop UE trace.
5. Based on UE log, evaluate the transition time: (Transition time at UE side = Time of last “RRC reconfiguration complete” – Time of “RRC Setup Request”).
6. Repeat steps 1-5 20 times.

NR RRC Inactive to NR RRC Connected latency in SA configuration

UE Triggered Transition

1. In the serving cell, ensure UE is in Inactive State and moved from its last Serving gNB to under the coverage of another gNB (actual).
2. Start UE and gNB traces.
3. Ping a server on the 5G Core Network to trigger a service request from UE.
4. Stop traces.

5. Based on UE and gNB logs, evaluate the transition time: (Transition time = “Path Switch Request Response” at gNB – Time of “RRC Connection Resume Request” at UE side).
6. Repeat steps 1-5 20 times.

Network Triggered Transition

1. In the serving cell, ensure UE is in Inactive State.
2. Start UE and gNB traces.
3. Trigger a RAN paging event (e.g. initiating an incoming user plane DL)
4. Observe that the UE switches to Connected mode.
5. Stop UE trace.
6. Based on UE and gNB logs, evaluate the transition time: (Transition time = Time of “Resuming from RRC Inactive” – “Paging UE Message”).
7. Repeat steps 1-6 20 times.

4.2.3.2.3 Success criteria

The metric to validate the tests shall be the transition times between states. Trial initiatives shall report on used trigger points to evaluate the state transitions times. Minimum 20 valid samples are required for result evaluation. The result will be calculated and reported as an average from these 20 samples. Result evaluation:

- Minimum value, maximum value and average value measured in msec
- Expected target value in SA configuration:
 - NGMN recommendations = Idle <-> Connected transition time \leq 10 ms [4]
 - NGMN recommendations = Inactive <-> Connected transition time \leq 10 ms.

4.2.3.2.4 Logging

The results of the tests should be summarized to the Table 15.

Table 15. Control plane latency test results logging

State Transition Latency	Min	Max	Median
Idle to Active			
Inactive to Connected			

4.2.4 Jitter

In mobile networks we measure the jitter as Packet Delay Variation. This shows us how the latency varies over time. The main factors that cause jitter are signal quality over the air interface, gNB load and jitter on the transport network. Poor air-interface signal quality may increase the packet error rate, which results in more packet retransmissions and segmentation. As a result, the number of lost packets and jitters increases [36].

4.2.4.1 Test setup

Jitter measurement in the 5G networks is one part of QoE measurements. The Rohde & Schwarz QualiPoc handheld network troubleshooting device, used in 5G-ROUTES project for network measurements, has an “Interactivity test” feature which we are using to measure jitter. The Interactivity test the best test suited for validating 5G-NR uRLLC applications.

The test concept is sending a continuous stream of UDP packets from client to server and back with an underlying realistic traffic pattern. The control-client and the server instances set up the session, including port negotiation and load balancing using TCP protocol. Session sender and reflector are the actual instances exchanging the stream of UDP packets.

The server has to be located as close to the network edge as possible [35].

4.2.4.2 Test configuration

For the latency variation tests there are two use-cases: eMBB service and URLLC service. The configuration options for these are following:

- Conf. 1 (eMBB service):
 - Sub-carrier spacing: 30 kHz for <6GHz deployment
 - CP length: 2.3us
 - TTI: 500us (14 symbols at 30kHz)
 - Deployment options: Urban Macro (< 6GHz)
 - System BW: no specific constraint but bandwidth value needs to be reported
 - Duplex mode: FDD mode, or TDD mode with DDDSU DL/UL ratio
- Conf. 2 (URLLC service):
 - Sub-carrier spacing: 60(30) kHz for <6GHz deployment
 - CP length: 1.2us
 - TTI: 125us
 - System BW: no specific constraint but bandwidth value needs to be reported
 - Number of layers: 1
 - Duplex mode: FDD mode, or TDD mode with DDDSU DL/UL ratio

For the Interactivity test the following pattern will be used:

- Pattern name: “eGaming real-time”
- Traffic shape: Bursty
- Packets per second: 1250
- Packet size: 100bytes
- Packet delay budget: 100ms
- Test duration: 10s
- Max packet error rate: 0.2

4.2.4.3 Test procedure and logging

1. Select sector pointing into the trial area.
2. Select a location in that cell (good, average and cell conditions) based on the cell grid:
 - Good conditions should be represented by $-90 \text{ dBm} < \text{SS-RSRP}$
 - Average conditions should be represented by $-100 \text{ dBm} < \text{SS-RSRP} < -90 \text{ dBm}$;
 - Cell edge conditions should be represented by $\text{SS-RSRP} < -100 \text{ dBm}$
3. Start the interactivity test on QualiPoc device
 - Perform multiple (at least 10) tests
 - Log round-trip latency statistics (min/median/max), round-trip latency 10th percentile, median and maximum value of the PDV

4.2.4.4 Success criteria

Jitter values less than 10ms are expected.

4.2.5 Connection density

Connection density refers to a total number of devices fulfilling a target QoS per unit area (per km²). Target QoS is set to ensure a system packet drop rate less than 1% under given packet arrival rate and packet size.

$$\text{Packet drop rate} = \frac{\text{Number of packets in outag}}{\text{Number of generated packets}},$$

where a packet is in outage if this packet failed to be successfully received by the destination receiver beyond packet dropping timer.

Connection density should be achieved for a limited bandwidth and number of TRxPs. The target QoS is to support delivery of a message of a certain size within a certain time and with a certain success probability, as specified in Report ITU-R M.2412-0 [6].

This requirement is defined for the purpose of evaluation in the mMTC usage scenario.

The target for connection density should be 1 000 000 device/km² in urban environment.

There are two possible evaluation methods to evaluate connection density requirement defined in ITU-R M.2410-0 [6]:

- non-full buffer system-level simulation;
- full-buffer system-level simulation followed by link-level simulation.

The number of simultaneous active connections per square kilometer could be extracted also from the gNB side.

4.2.5.1 Non-full buffer system-level simulation

This test procedure is used to evaluate the connection density based on non-full buffer system-level simulation

4.2.5.1.1 Test procedure

- Set system user number per TRxP as N .
- Generate the user packet according to the traffic model.
- Run non-full buffer system-level simulation to obtain the packet outage rate. The outage rate is defined as the ratio of the number of packets that failed to be delivered to the destination receiver within a transmission delay of less than or equal to 10s to the total number of packets generated in *Step 2*.
- Change the value of N and repeat *Step 2-3* to obtain the system user number per TRxP N' satisfying the packet outage rate of 1%.
- Calculate connection density by equation $C = N'/A$ where the TRxP area A is calculated as $A = \frac{ISD^2 \sqrt{3}}{6}$, and ISD is the inter-site distance.

4.2.5.1.2 Success criteria

The requirement is fulfilled if the connection density C is greater than or equal to the connection density requirement defined in Report ITU-R M.2410-0 (1 000 000 devices per km²).

4.2.5.1.3 Logging

The simulation bandwidth used to fulfill the requirement should be reported. Additionally, it is encouraged to report the connection efficiency (measured as N' divided by simulation bandwidth) for the achieved connection density.

4.2.5.2 Full buffer system-level simulation

This test procedure is used to evaluate the connection density based on full buffer system-level simulation.

4.2.5.2.1 Test procedure

The following steps are used to evaluate the connection density based on full-buffer system-level simulation followed by link-level simulation.

1. Perform full-buffer system-level simulation using the evaluation parameters for Urban Macro-mMTC test environment, determine the uplink $SS-SINR_i$ for each percentile $i=1...99$ of the distribution over users, and record the average allocated user bandwidth W_{user} .
 - In case UE multiplexing on the same time/frequency resource is modelled in this step, record the average number of multiplexed users N_{mux} . $N_{mux} = 1$ for no UE multiplexing.
2. Perform link-level simulation and determine the achievable user data rate R_i for the recorded $SS-SINR_i$ and W_{user} values.
 - In case UE multiplexing on the same time/frequency resource is modelled in this step, record the average number of multiplexed users $n_{mux,i}$ under $SS-SINR_i$. The achievable data rate for this case is derived by $R_i = Z_i/n_{mux,i}$, where aggregated bit rate Z_i is the summed bit rate of $n_{mux,i}$ users on W_{user} . $n_{mux,i} = 1$ for no UE multiplexing.
3. Calculate the packet transmission delay of a user as $D_i = S/R_i$, where S is the packet size.
4. Calculate the traffic generated per user as $T = S/T_{inter-arrival}$, where $T_{inter-arrival}$ is the inter packet arrival time.
5. Calculate the long-term frequency resource requested under $SS-SINR_i$ as $B_i = T/(R_i/W_{user})$.
6. Calculate the number of supported connections per TRxP, $N = W / mean(B_i)$. W is the simulation bandwidth. The mean of B_i may be taken over the best 99% of the $SS-SINR_i$ conditions.
 - In case UE multiplexing is modelled in Step 1, $N = N_{mux} \times W / mean(B_i)$. In case UE multiplexing is modelled in Step 2, $N = W / mean(B_i/n_{mux,i})$.
7. Calculate the connection density as $C = N / A$, where the TRxP area A is calculated as $A = \frac{ISD^2\sqrt{3}}{6}$, and ISD is the inter-site distance

4.2.5.2.2 Success criteria

The requirement is fulfilled if the connection density C is greater than or equal to the connection density requirement defined in Report ITU-R M.2410-0 (1 000 000 devices per km^2).

4.2.5.2.3 Logging

The simulation bandwidth used to fulfill the requirement should be reported. Additionally, it is encouraged to report the connection efficiency (measured as N' divided by simulation bandwidth) for the achieved connection density.

4.2.5.3 Measuring connection density from NG-RAN

Connection density is also possible to be measured from the NG-RAN using Network Manager

4.2.5.3.1 Test setup

For measuring the number of simultaneous connections per square kilometer, which are active (exchanging data with the network) a counter available in gNB "Number of 5G system connected users" could be used. Counter reports an average number of connected users in the cell in the reporting period. [23]

4.2.5.3.2 Test procedure

- Generate x number of virtual connections to gNB.

- Collect data from gNB using counter “Number of 5G system connected users”. Use minimal 15 minutes granularity for reporting.
- Extract data from the gNB using Network Manager

4.2.5.3.3 Logging

The Network Management software will log service availability in available format.

4.2.6 Reliability

4.2.6.1 Test setup

Reliability testing should be done in the following settings.

- Scenario 1. 1 UE – 1 BS.
 - Test the UL and DL reliability as the UE moves from good coverage to worse coverage (until the UE is out of coverage).
- Scenario 2. 1 UE – multiple BSs
 - Test the DL reliability in different interference scenarios (starting with minimum interference to the worst-case interference where all interfering BSs are pointing their main beam towards the UE).
- Scenario 3. Multiple UEs– multiple BSs
 - Test the UL reliability in different interference scenarios.
- Scenario 4. Multiple UEs - 1 BS
 - Test the UL and DL reliability as the test UE moves from good coverage to worse coverage while other UEs are connected to the same BS and have UL or DL traffic.

4.2.6.2 Test configuration

Conf. 1 (eMBB service):

- NR TDD SA Deployment
- System BW: 100 MHz for TDD < 6 GHz
- 30kHz sub-carrier spacing
- CP length: 2.3μs
- TTI length: 0.5ms
- DL peak rate test: DL/UL ratio: full DL
- UL peak rate test: DL/UL ratio: full UL

Conf. 2 (URLLC service):

- NR TDD/FDD SA Deployment
- System BW: 100 MHz for TDD / 10 MHz for FDD
- 60kHz/15kHz sub-carrier spacing (TDD/FDD)
- CP length: 1.2μs
- TTI length: 0.125ms
- DL peak rate test: DL/UL ratio: full DL
- UL peak rate test: DL/UL ratio: full UL

4.2.6.3 Test procedure

The following test procedures are defined for the reliability tests:

1. Select sector pointing into the trial area and make sure that only one test UE is connected to this sector.
 - a. Scenario 1. Make sure that all interfering cells are either not transmitting or are not pointing their main beam to the test UE.
 - b. Scenario 2. Have all interfering BSs transmit towards the coverage area of the serving cell of the test UE.
 - c. Scenario 3. Have all interfering UEs transmit in the UL to generate interference to the test UE.
 - d. Scenario 4. Make sure that all interfering cells are either not transmitting or are not pointing their main beam to the test UE. Make sure all background UEs are connected to the same BS as test UE and have some UL or DL traffic.
2. Start moving the test UE from the cell center towards the cell edge in scenario 1 and from low interference to high interference conditions in scenarios 2 and 3.
3. Perform a download/upload from/to UE using UDP or TCP (using iperf).
4. Log the reliability as defined in the section 4.1.6.
5. Repeat steps 3-5 several times with different locations and traffic load.

4.2.6.4 Success criteria

For reliability, the expected output would depend on the use case.

For eMBB, the requirement on reliability for one transmission of a packet of 32 bytes with a user plane latency of 8ms is recommended to be at least 10^{-2} .

A general URLLC reliability requirement for one transmission of a packet is $1-10^{-5}$ for 32 bytes with a user plane latency of 1ms [4].

For mobility use cases, the requirements for communication reliability and user plane latency of delivery of a packet of size 300 bytes is $1-10^{-5}$ with a user plane latency of 3-10 msec.

4.2.7 Position accuracy

For evaluating performance of NR positioning technologies, the following metrics apply.

1. Horizontal accuracy. The difference between the calculated horizontal position and the actual horizontal position of a UE. The Cumulative Distribution Functions (CDFs) of horizontal positioning errors are used as a performance metrics in NR positioning evaluations. The following percentiles of positioning errors are analyzed: 50%, 67%, 80%, 90%.
2. Vertical accuracy. The difference between the calculated vertical position and the actual vertical position of a UE. Vertical error is not necessarily applicable to all solutions and/or scenarios. In terms of applicability, the CDFs of vertical positioning errors are used as a performance metrics in NR positioning evaluations. The following percentiles of positioning error are analyzed 50%, 67%, 80%, 90%.

In the 5G-ROUTES use-cases we assess the horizontal accuracy. More details can be found in D2.5 where different technologies are identified to be used in the trails.

4.2.7.1 Test setup

At least two different vendor 5G capable UE-s for measuring the horizontal accuracy are needed. The validation of positioning accuracy will be done by comparing the measurements of position from 5G network with UE-s with the measurement using GNSS locations.

4.2.7.1.1 Test procedure

- Measure position with UE-s from 2 different vendor (and chipset). In at least 10 locations the measurements should be made with UE-1 and UE-2.
- On the same spot where the location coordinates were acquired measure position with using GNSS
- Calculate the difference between the measurement with using 5G network and with using GNSS
 - Calculate differences using UE1 and UE2 coordinates and take an average of results
- The accuracy will be provided in meters.

4.2.7.1.2 Success criteria

Position accuracy is the difference between the measured and the real position. It is stated in 3GPP TR 38.855 that for Rel 16 that the horizontal positioning error must be less or equal than 50 m for 80% of the UEs [32]. In 3GPP TR 38.855 [32] it is also additionally stated that as a starting point for commercial use cases, the horizontal positioning error should be less than 10 m for 80% of UEs in outdoor deployments scenarios which we will keep as a success criteria for 5G REL-16 network PI. As stated in D2.5 our simulations have shown that horizontal positioning error less than 1 m for 80% of UEs could be achieved. Although the requirements for the use-cases in the 5G-ROUTES project can be in some cases less than 1m, this could only be achievable with using a hybrid solution as proposed in D2.5 and can even get to cm level.

4.2.7.1.3 Logging

The template, shown in Table 16, should be used for logging the measurement accuracy.

Table 16. Logging position accuracy

Measurement no	UE-1 location coordinates	UE-2 location coordinates	GNSS location coordinates	Calculated accuracy (m)
1...10				

4.2.8 Coverage

Coverage is the land area covered by the 5G signal divided by the total land area. The following sections will be dividing the trials into outdoor single-cell coverage, outdoor multi-cell continuous coverage, outdoor to indoor coverage and indoor coverage respectively.

Alternatively, to the coverage measurements the coverage can also be calculated with specific software and this will be done to refine the measurement results. It is especially important for the coverage on the sea area. [2]

4.2.8.1 Outdoor Single-cell Coverage

The coverage performance will be tested in UL and DL, in control and data channels, in terms of both the maximum distances in LOS and NLOS conditions, and the corresponding data rates at cell edge. The benefits of various coverage enhancing features (e.g. Tx diversity) at gNB or UE should also be investigated. Coverage in this section is based on a mobile broadband data service, therefore the success criteria is an achieved data rate in a geographical area [2].

4.2.8.1.1 Test setup

This test case will have one cell under test in a minimum of a 7-cell deployment environment (Figure 15). Dense urban, urban macro and rural deployments scenarios are considered according to section 3.1.1. Frequency reuse factor is 1.

Figure 15. Seven-cell deployment

4.2.8.1.2 Test configuration

Interference on control channel only

This configuration focuses on the interference from neighboring cells on the control channel only, by turning on the 6 cells (broadcasting channel and synchronization channel are on) without any users or traffic, i.e. no interference on the data channel. Tests should be carried out on UL and DL separately

Interference on control and data channel

This configuration focuses on the interference from neighboring cells on both the control and data channels, to create interference across the operating bandwidth. The level of the interference can be controlled by the allowed traffic in neighbor cells. Tests should be carried out on UL and DL separately.

1. **Downlink.** 50% interference level from neighbor cell both for control channel and data channel. The definition of 50% interference level is that 50% downlink transmission PRB are randomly chosen to transmit interference signal.
2. **Uplink.** lead to Y dB uplink Interference over Thermal (IoT) rise for test cell. The definition of Y dB IoT rise is that the received interference noise from the UEs of neighbor cell uplink transmission should lead to Y dB rise of the receivers' noise power

4.2.8.1.3 Test procedure

1. Activate cell under test

2. Activate surrounding cells
3. Configure cells according to test configuration (interference on control channel only, interference on control and data channel)
4. Place end user devices in the cell under test and establish data connections.
 - Optionally place scanner at same end user device location
5. Move end user devices throughout the cell area and log data according to logging section
 - Optionally move scanner with end user device and log data according to logging section

4.2.8.1.4 Success criteria

The coverage area achieving the data rates specified in section 4.2.8.1.5 should be recorded and compared to LTE coverage for the same frequency band or accounting for the coverage difference in the case of different frequency bands for 5G NR and LTE

4.2.8.1.5 Logging

- For the coverage performance of the control channel and the data channel in DL and UL respectively, various channels' maximum path losses and coverage distances could be recorded, e.g. PDSCH, PUSCH, PDCCH, PUCCH. By comparing the coverage differences among channels, the limiting channel and its data rate at the coverage edge should be measured.
- Vice versa, the coverage distances that correspond to the following low data rates should be investigated.
 - UL: 512kbps, 1Mbps;
 - DL: 1Mbps, 2Mbps.

Note that these values are used for LTE testing and can be a baseline/reference for measurement.

- The control channel coverage should be measured and compared among different schemes:
 - PDCCH: choose a baseline transmission scheme, and two or more optional schemes for comparison:
 - Single wide beam (LTE like)
 - Single wide beam with repeated transmission
 - Narrow beam sweeping (the number of beams should be configurable)

Repeat with DL interference from neighbor cells

- PUCCH
 - Baseline: long duration single-slot transmission
 - Compare to Long duration multi-slot transmission

Repeat with UL interference from neighbor cells

Repeat with UL enhancement, i.e. UE transmit diversity

- PBCH and synchronization channel
 - Cell search (SSS and PSS) and successful PBCH demodulation
 - Compare different transmission schemes listed in the PDCCH tests

Repeat with UL/DL interference from neighbor cells separately.

Parameters defined below will be measured and recorded during the drive / walk test. Additionally, location information is stored. In consequence, the measured parameters can be plotted for a certain geographical area and thus a realistic coverage map is generated. The results should be logged as in Table 17.

Table 17. Parameters for DL/UL data and control channels

	SS-RSRP	SS-RSRQ	SS-SINR	GPS location	Distance to BS	Throughput	LOS/ NLOS
PDSCH							

PUSCH							
PDCCH							
PUCCH							

In cases where it is not possible to measure data/control channel signal strength & quality, for DL coverage, it is also practical to measure DL Throughput vs. SS-RSRP and/or CSI-RSRP.

Optionally reference measurements could be provided by the scanner. In this case parameters should be logged as in Table 18.

Table 18. Parameters for scanner logging in SUL tests

	Signal power	SS-SINR	GPS location	Distance to BS
PBCH				
PSS				
SSS				
	SS-RSRP	SS-SINR	GPS location	Distance to BS
CSI-RS				

4.2.8.2 Outdoor Multi-Cell Continuous Coverage

This test case focuses on the continuous connectivity across multiple cells, hence it will provide guidance on deployment parameters such as inter-site distance, SS-RSRP, SS-RSRQ, NR RSSI and SS-SINR. It is also important to consider the impact of traffic load and interference on coverage. When the traffic load increases, the noise floor of the BS and the mobile will increase and their sensitivity will decrease, leading to shrinking coverage area. Additionally, SUL functional performance needs to be tested, and the difference in single-user and multi-user coverage test should be measured and analyzed [2].

4.2.8.2.1 Test setup

Same as for Outdoor Single-cell Coverage

4.2.8.2.2 Test configuration

Same as for Outdoor Single-cell Coverage

4.2.8.2.3 Test procedure

1. Activate cell under test
2. Activate surrounding cells
3. Record the cell configuration (3.5GHz/700MHz), including direction, down-tilt angle, 5GNR BS and UE transmit power
4. Configure cells according to test configuration (interference on control channel only, interference on control and data channel, record UL/DL interference level and thermal noise levels; preferably carry out the tests in low interference and noise locations.
5. The 5G end user device will be placed on the test vehicle and transmit/receive full-buffer UDP packets. The drive route should cover multiple cells and handover between cells should happen successfully. The duration of such test should exceed 30min. Log data according to section 3.5.2.1.4
 - Optionally move scanner with end user device and log data according to section 3.5.2.1.5
6. (SUL testing only) turn off SUL function, UE goes into 3.5GHz cell, stop near the BS tower and start FTP UL/DL continuous packet transmission or video service or live broadcasting service, etc. UE moves away from the cell center, until UE loses connection. The duration of such process should last at least 10

minutes to ensure the links are stable and enough data is captured.

7. (SUL testing only) turn on SUL function, and repeat step 6

4.2.8.2.4 *Success criteria*

The coverage area achieving the data rates specified in section 4.2.8.1.5 should be recorded.

4.2.8.2.5 *Logging*

- The device should log various data including SS-RSRP, SS-SINR, UL/DL PDCP data rates, UL/DL MCS, UL/DL RB# per TTI, UL transmit power, DL transmission scheme, PDCCH SS-SINR, DL PDSCH DMRS SS-SINR, number of data streams, BLER.
- The gNB should record UL SS-SINR, PUSCH SS-SINR, PUCCH SS-SINR, UL IoT level.
- SUL testing additional recording requirement: test location information, UL/DL data rate on each frequency band and relative ratio with and without SUL, UE operating frequency bands; UL cell edge data rate (e.g. 500kbps, 1Mbps, 2Mbps...) and its corresponding RSPS so as to calculate SUL effective region; signaling latency due to frequency band change.

4.2.8.3 *Outdoor to Indoor Coverage*

This test case analyses how well an outdoor BS covers the indoor users, whether they are distributed at a ground level, or across multiple floors. This helps understand the penetration loss due to building structure/materials, and the reachable depth with horizontal and vertical beamforming enhancement [2].

In 5G-ROUTES project context we have indoor coverage in the train and ferry where this test setup will apply.

4.2.8.3.1 *Test setup*

In this case we have a stand-alone cell covering a building whereas measurements are executed within the building. Dense urban deployments scenarios are considered according to section 3.1.1. The setup is illustrated in the Figure 16.

Figure 16. SA cell covering a building

Building coverage

Test the coverage performance inside the building (or train/ ferry) within the trial area. Test coverage on the whole route of the ferry/ train and for the ferry case on different floors. This test will record the power stats and the link quality stats at the UE, the SINRs and noise floor at the BS. UE can be 23dBm or 26dBm with Tx diversity

Penetration test

The difference to the previous test case is to learn the coverage performance of the 5G BS at very difficult indoor locations, where the penetration loss is prohibitive. Such locations can be in deep inside of the ferry or on the lower floors and the more shielded cabins of the train.

This case is designed for testing beamforming capability of the BS and typical values of indoor penetration loss. This case can be reused for coverage of massive connections.

4.2.8.3.2 Test procedure

1. Activate cell under test
2. 4G devices and 5G devices are placed side by side, optionally place scanner at same end user device location
3. Activate data connection of the devices
4. Measure parameters for data and control channels when moving from LOS (close to window) locations to NLOS (into the building) locations. The focus is on the downlink control channel, which will deploy adaptive beamforming or a single wide beam with repeated transmission. Optionally move scanner with end user device.
5. SUL testing:
 - a. Turn off SUL, UE connects to 3.5GHz NR cell, move around the building and floors, ensure places where SS-RSRP drops below -110dBm are included;
 - b. when multiple UEs are used, ensure all places within the building are measured, put UE distribution as excellent/good/med/bad=1:2:4:3;
 - c. turn on SUL and repeat the above process.

4.2.8.3.3 Success criteria

The coverage area achieving the data rates specified in section 4.2.8.1.5 should be recorded.

4.2.8.3.4 Logging

- The device should log various data including SS-RSRP, SS-SINR, UL/DL PDCP data rates, UL/DL MCS, UL/DL RB# per TTI, UL transmit power, DL transmission scheme, PDCCH SS-SINR, DL PDSCH SS-SINR, number of data streams, BLER.
- The gNB should record UL SS-SINR, PUSCH SS-SINR, PUCCH SS-SINR, UL IoT level.
- SUL testing additional recording requirement: test location information, UL/DL data rate on each frequency band and relative ratio with and without SUL, UE operating frequency bands; UL cell edge data rate (e.g. 500kbps, 1Mbps, 2Mbps...) and its corresponding RSPS so as to calculate SUL effective region; signaling latency due to frequency band change.

4.2.8.4 Indoor Coverage

This section is mainly intended to understand the indoor coverage. There are several aspects to consider when trying to understand indoor coverage, which may be different from the outdoor scenario [2].

4.2.8.4.1 Test setup

- Indoor environment, e.g. inside train or ferry, LOS or NLOS according to section 3.1.1
- BS placement: on ceiling or wall-mounted
- The UL and DL coverage should be balanced, i.e. measurement result should be able to advise whether loss of connection is caused by UL or DL, and by which channel.

4.2.8.4.2 Test configuration

Tests may be carried out in a single cell deployment, whether multi-cell coverage can be tested depends on the progress of trials.

4.2.8.4.3 Test procedure

1. Activate cell under test
2. Place 5G end user devices (Optionally place scanner at same end user device location)
3. Activate data connection of the devices
4. Measure parameters defined in section 4.2.8.1.5 for data and control channels when moving within the indoor location (Optionally move scanner with end user device).

4.2.8.4.4 Success criteria

The coverage area achieving the data rates specified in section 4.2.8.1.5 should be recorded

4.2.8.4.5 Logging

Same as for Outdoor Single-cell Coverage

4.2.9 Availability

Network availability is the amount of uptime in a network system over a specific time interval.

It is calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{Availability} = \frac{\text{Uptime}}{\text{Total time (Uptime+Downtime)}}$$

Service availability is “one minus maximum tolerable packet loss rate at the transport layer for that application”

4.2.9.1.1 Test setup

In 5G-ROUTES project we will measure service availability by evaluating service operational state of NG-RAN node cells which are providing service to UE used.

For measuring service availability, the “Cell availability” counter will be used. This counter is available in NG-RAN gNB and is reporting the length of time that a cell is available for service.

4.2.9.1.2 Test procedure

- Measure “cell availability” for the test site using the counter provided in gNB
- Use minimal reporting period of 15 minutes.

4.2.9.1.3 Success criteria

Availability of >99.999% should be achieved for all the use-cases

4.2.9.1.4 Logging

The Network Management software will log service availability in available format.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable focuses on describing the network level Performance Indicators which are the most important metrics to validate the 5G network features for Connected and Automotive Mobility. Comprehensive test methodologies for measuring and evaluating the PIs are defined. The success criteria for the PIs come from the ITU and 3GPP requirements for the 5G network features but also are taking into account the requirements for the 5G-ROUTES project use-cases. In the next stages of the project if needed KPIs can be selected from the PIs described in this document. Those will be then described in D1.6.

The most important outcome for the project is giving harmonized test methodologies which can be used on all the test facilities to get comparable results. They are giving the most value for the project in the network deployment stage (D3.1) where the after the installation works the 5G network will be assessed and fine-tuned to meet the given PIs. The results from network measurements will be saved in the Tenant Web portal (D2.7). As they are based on work from NGMN, ITU and 3GPP they are also comparable with similar projects.

This deliverable will be used for testing 5G networks after the deployment of the networks to assure that it is ready for real field trials with 5G-ROUTES use-cases and can deliver meaningful results. Those use-cases are highly dependent on the 5G connectivity, hence providing a solid foundation for network validation is vital.

As the testing and validating the 5G network features is somewhat dependent on the actual hardware and software configuration used, the deliverable describes more options than are needed for the validation. In the final version of this deliverable will be described the actual test configurations and devices used in each location.

6 References

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